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Biodiversity

CalitaTerra

Sanogeneous Food

Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality

Ideas and Concepts

News

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EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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This multidisciplinary and comparative Joint Exchange programme will identify and examine how nutritional labeling in European countries and out of Europe can influence on health and welfare of population. Health professionals agree that the relationship between diet and health is important. Our eating habits can help or hurt our overall health and well-being. Good eating habits include being a smart shopper and selecting foods that reflect the Dietary Guidelines. The food label was designed to help people choose foods for a healthful diet. By using the food label, we can compare the nutrient content of similar foods, see how foods fit into our overall diets, and understand the relationship between certain nutrients and diseases.

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Editorial Column

„WATER INTERNATIONAL DAY TOPIC: WATER IN CARPATHIANS. WATER FROM CARPATHIANS”

Water is the most dynamic component of the natural environment, and it presents to be the most important natural resource. Regardless of how it will be studied, like water for the next generations or like water for the future, it will remain the most important, limited and vulnerable natural resource that is currently available. It becomes a fundamental fight to avoid a planetary crisis of water and especially freshwater.

In the current context of climate change, the freshwater issues are becoming more acute. Experts from the European Commission say that lately, extreme heat and drought had cost the EU budget over 100 billion.

This, while 20% of the water currently used in Europe is wasted, and the percentage is growing, and can reach 40%. Moreover, in present, 400 million people worldwide suffer from lack of water and according to the United Nations in 2050 their number will reach 4 billion(!).

As a result of the concerns of increasingly large groups of people aware of the danger water crisis, every year on March 22 it is celebrated The World Water Day. United Nations General Assembly announced the period 2005-2015 as the International Decade "Water for Life" in order to increase knowledge, which will cause real actions.

The International Decade goals are to increase awareness on water issues from all points of view (water in food, agriculture, tourism and generally in all economic activities, with oceans and seas of the world) and at all levels.

It also follows the purpose of creating favorable conditions for organizations and individuals interested for water projects and tangential programs, to ensure global goals set in terms of water issues

Celebrating World Water Day aims to bring public attention to issues related to the need to protect water quality and quantity and to put in its true light the role, duties and responsibilities of those in charge, but also all of us in maintenance, recovery and protection of water sources.

In this context we consider highly desirable to introduce in Romanian public perception, and not only among nature lovers, travel or healthy eating, a appreciation of the idea of water. And this, especially in fragile areas like the mountain that are actually the ecozones of the genesis of freshwater.

Therefore, let's support the idea: **WATER IN CARPATHIANS. WATER FROM CARPATHIANS”**

Professor Romulus GRUIA, PhD
Director of the Journal of EcoAgriTourism

SUMMARY

	Editorial	
1	"WATER INTERNATIONAL DAY TOPIC: WATER IN CARPATHIANS. WATER FROM CARPATHIANS" Romulus GRUIA	
	Biodiversity	
5	FORMATION OF AROMATIC PROFILE OF ROSE TABLE WINES MADE OF PINOT NOIR AND CABERNET-SAUVIGNO M. BILKO, A. TENETKA	
10	VEGETABLE OILS EXTRACTION BY PRESSING OLEAGINOUS SEEDS: THE INFLUENCE FACTORS A.O. ARISANU	
	CalitaTerra	
14	INNOVATIVE IDEAS FOR THE OPTIMIZATION OF THE POTATO SORTING PROCESS F. V. EDU	
18	RESEARCH IR SPECTRA PECTINS AND GELS ON THEIR BASIS I. KRAPYVNYTSKA, D. PRASOL, F. PERTCEVOI, T. KUZNETSAVA	
23	LOW TEMPERATURE EXTRACTION OF PLANTS BY LIQUIFICATE GASES WASTE OF CHOKEBERRY FRUITS P. MERDZHANOV, M. ANGELOVA-ROMOVA, N. NENOV, M. ZLATANOV, G. ANTOVA, T. ATANASOVA, P. DENEV, A. STOYANOVA	
	Sanogeneous Food	
28	EXISTENT AND PROPOSED SYSTEMS FOR POTATO SORTING F. V. EDU, C. Csatlos	
32	STUDY REGARDING THE CRUSHING RESISTANCE OF OLEAGINOUS SUNFLOWER SEEDS A.O. ARISANU, F. RUS	
	Sustainable Tourism and Hospitality	
39	KAZAKHSTAN AT THE TURN OF THE 21 ST CENTURY G. SYDYKBAYEVA	
42	INFLUENCE OF HEAT TREATMENT AND PRE-PACKAGING ON QUALITY OF BALANCED PRODUCTS N.S. RODIONIVA, A. BIRCA, E.S. POPOV, T.I. BAKHTINA	
	Ideas and Concepts	
46	RESEARCH ON THE RELATIVE POSITIONS OF CABLE CAR DURING EXTERNAL MECHANICAL DISTURBANCES E. HODIRNAU, M. HODIRNAU	
51	DEVELOPMENT OF MODULE FOR DETERMINING THE TEMPERATURE FIELD IN THE HIGH PRESSURE CHAMBER S. SOKOLOV, N. SEVATOROV, I. SELEZNEVA	

	<p>55</p> <p>62</p> <p>68</p> <p>71</p>	<p><i>THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON REDUCING PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS IN SUNFLOWER SEED KERNELS</i> P. Gurskyi, D. Biduk, D. Prasol, F. Pertsevyi</p> <p><i>THERMODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF HEAT EXCHANGING APPLIANCES</i> V. Shutyuk, Samiylenko Sergiy, Vasylenko Sergiy</p> <p><i>BIOTECHNOLOGY IN THE MEAT INDUSTRY</i> S. MELNYCHUK, L. BAL-PRYLIPKO</p> <p><i>APPLICATIONS IN PRECISION AGRICULTURE OF STABILIZATION SYSTEMS WITH MICRO-SENSORS FOR PHOTO AND VIDEO CAMERAS</i> M. MANESCU · L. CRISTEA · D.C. OLA · B. BRAUN</p>
	News	
77		NEEFOOD 2013

FORMATION OF AROMATIC PROFILE OF ROSE TABLE WINES MADE OF PINOT NOIR AND CABERNET-SAUVIGNON

M. BILKO A. TENETKA

Abstract: *This research article presents the study of the aromatic complex of pink table wines. The objects of research were rose dry wines made of Pinot Noir and Cabernet-Sauvignon. Wines were prepared in conditions of micro winemaking by the schemes that included processing without maceration, maceration on mash 3 and 6 hours, mash fermentation to alcohol content by 2% vol. All samples were organoleptically evaluated, which revealed that rose wines from Pinot Noir have more bright and varied aromas. Then varietal characteristics started to appear in wines of Cabernet Sauvignon.*

Also in the obtained samples the qualitative composition and quantitative content of aroma complex by gas-liquid chromatography was determined. The percentage of the main groups of substances responsible for the aroma of pink table wines was determined. Main representatives of the higher alcohols, esters, acids, and lactones, which cause particular flavor of this type of wine, were found.

Keywords: *rose wine, aroma compounds, berry tones, Pinot Noir, Cabernet Sauvignon, lactones, higher alcohols, esters, fatty acids, gas-liquid chromatography.*

1. Introduction

The Aroma is one of the main wine quality indicators. Along with the color it can play a paramount role. Its feature is the presence of fruit and berry tones in aroma of rose wines - barberry, dogwood, raspberry, strawberry, red currant. Dairy tones (including cream) are also quite common [2,6,9]. In contrast to wines with varietal aroma characters, determining factors in the formation of rose wines aromatic profile are technological methods of processing grapes and fermentation conditions, e.g. yeast strain [1,8,10].

The main stage in the flavor formation of this type of wine occurs during fermentation, when the majority of fruity flavored esters and feraneols are formed. [4,8,9].

Various aromatic compounds can contribute differently in formation of aromatic profiles of rosés depending on their concentrations in the wines and the presence of other components that may enhance aromatic aspects of each other on the principle of synergy [5,7].

For example, terpenoids, fatty acid, ethyl esters (mainly isoamil acetate), diacetyl, oktalakton in the edges of the threshold concentration have a positive impact on the aroma of rose wines. In small quantities diacetyl can raise "red fruity" flavor that is entirely appropriate for fresh rose. Sulfur-containing components are also responsible for vegetable wine characteristics. They are undesirable elements and their

appearance is avoided by selecting of a certain yeast strain [2,4,7,9].

In general the problem of aromatic profile formation of rose wines is very important. At present rose wine sales are second only to white wines, and therefore there is nothing surprising in an increased attention of the scientific community to problems related to the preservation of properties of these wines. That is why the study of the influence of various factors on the formation of the aromatic profile of rose table wines is an actual problem.

The aim of this work was to study the aroma complex of rose table wines that were made of different grape varieties.

The tasks of the research were:

1. To identify the impact of various aromatic components on organoleptic properties of rose table wine.
2. To identify and quantify the aromatic composition of rose table wine.

2. Materials and methods

The objects of research were rose dry wine made of Pinot Noir and Cabernet-Sauvignon that were cultivated in sufficient quantity in Ukraine, with sugar content of 170 and 210 g/dm³ respectively. The samples were prepared in conditions of micro winemaking by the schemes that included processing without maceration, maceration on mash 3 and 6 hours, mash fermentation to alcohol content by 2% vol.

Fermentation was conducted on pure culture of yeast-killers K-47 selected in NUGaW "Magarach". The mash was treated with sulfite by potassium bisulfite (Döhler company) at doses of 50-75 mg/dm³.

Determination of qualitative and quantitative composition of aromatic complex was determined by gas-liquid chromatography.

3. Results and discussions

After wine preparation an industrial degustation was carried out, the results of the organoleptic characteristic of rose table wines made from grapes Pinot Noir and Cabernet-Sauvignon are presented in table 1.

№	Name of sample	Organoleptic characteristics	Overall score
1.	Pinot Noir (in white without maceration)	Aroma is bright. Expressed tone of lollipops and strawberries with raspberries.	7,65
2.	Pinot noir (maceration on mash 3 hours)	The aromas of red berries - barberry, strawberry and raspberry. In the latest "nose" - raspberries and cream.	7,8
3.	Pinot noir (maceration on mash 6 hours)	Berry tones in the aroma - red currants, strawberries.	7,8
4.	Pinot noir (fermentation 1 day, 2% vol. alc.)	In flavor barberry, currant and other red berries. There is a faint creamy tone.	7,85
5.	Pinot Noir (in red, fermentation 2 days, 5% vol. alc.)	Flavor berry milk. Good feel raspberries and red currants.	7,7
6.	Cabernet Sauvignon (in white without maceration)	Aroma is not bright, with strawberry tones.	7,5
7.	Cabernet Sauvignon (maceration on mash 3 hours)	Berry aroma, not very developed, with cream and strawberry-raspberry shades.	7,6

Aromatic profiles of samples were received according to the results of the tasting (fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1 Aroma profiles of rose table wines made of Pinot Noir variety

Fig. 2 Aroma profiles of rose table wines made of Cabernet Sauvignon variety

The figures show that wines from Pinot Noir have more bright and varied aromas. Then as in wines of Cabernet Sauvignon varietal characteristics started to appear. The next stage of our research was to determine the qualitative composition and quantitative content of aroma complex of samples.

After receiving the results of chromatography all aromatic components were divided into several groups: higher alcohols, acids, esters, lactones and other components, that include aldehydes, cyclic and aliphatic hydrocarbons saturated and unsaturated character, which were met in small concentrations. (fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Main groups of compounds that form aroma complex of rose table wine made from grapes Pinot Noir and Cabernet-Sauvignon

As can we see from the diagram, most of aroma compounds are higher alcohols. Of these, about 60-70% of alcohols with short hydrocarbon chain (C1-C5). It is known that alcohols with longer hydrocarbon chain have a pleasant fragrance at low concentrations. Instead, butyl, amyl alcohols and their isomers have very unpleasant odor, but they, along with esters, aldehydes and other components form the so-called "wine background" [4,10]. Main part of higher alcohols in all samples constitutes isoamyl and β -phenylethyl alcohol. The last has a pleasant mild floral scent of roses, hyacinth and honey [1,7].

His percent in the samples made of Pinot Noir is 12-22 of the total content of higher alcohols, when Cabernet Sauvignon samples contain 28-30%.

Among other alcohols tryptophol, that was measured in high concentrations, has a very unpleasant smell, but at a dilution and combination with other substances it becomes a very nice and pleasant flavor [1,6]. As well as benzyl alcohol, which has exquisite floral fragrance (its amount correlates with the tasting score with a coefficient of 0.82) [7]. Other alcohols with pleasant aromas that were detected

in the experimental samples were hexanol, heptanol, octanol, nonanol, α -bysabolol and tyrozol.

Table 2 shows the mass concentration (mg/dm³) of main alcohols that were detected in the experimental samples.

Table 2. Mass concentration of higher alcohols in the samples of rose table wine

Nº of sample	Isoamyl alcohol	Isobutyl alcohol	β -phenylethyl alcohol	Tryptophol	Benzyl alcohol	Hexanol
1	210,8	48,5	72,57	1,76	0,17	1,51
2	170,3	41,5	62,26	1,74	0,49	2,38
3	89,7	19,8	53,4	1,19	0,43	1,68
4	105,1	49,5	41,04	0,78	0,85	3,4
5	237,8	92,5	52,82	1,15	0,7	6,7
6	163,5	27,3	99,16	10,26	0,07	1,77
7	145,9	28,5	88,34	9,72	0,1	1,57

Esters made the most diverse group among aromatic compounds that were present in the experimental samples of rose table wine. Although this group constitutes only 7-12% of the total number of aromatic substances, it has a significant influence on the aromatic profile because esters have fairly low threshold concentrations of flavor [2,3,4]. Moreover, the esters concentration impacted the tasting score (correlation coefficient 0.83). There were such esters as ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate, butyrate, isoamil acetate, hexil acetate, ethyl caprylate and ethyl capronate whose presence, from written sources, is one of rosé wines markers [2,4,7]. It should be also noted the increases in amounts of isoamil acetate, β -phenyl ethyl acetate, ethyl caprylate and ethyl lactate, were observed in samples with higher tasting scores. According to the publications, ethyl lactate concentration in

wines can reach 200 mg/dm³, which in turn can lead to an appearance in wine of unpleasant heavy tones [2,6]. In the experimental samples its quantity was less than 1.8 mg/dm³ and it increased proportionally to an increase in duration of maceration.

As it is known long chain esters have a more pleasant fruity flavor than short chain esters [3,9]. Cabernet Sauvignon wines were characterized by a wide range of esters, including long chain. For example, a large numbers of esters of caprylic, caproic, lauric, vanillic and succinic acids were detected. All these compounds have pleasant fruity and floral aromas. [9]

Table 3 shows the mass concentration (mg/dm³) of main esters that were detected in the experimental samples.

Table 3. Mass concentration of main esters in the experimental samples of rose table wine

Nº	Isoamil acetate	β -phenyl ethyl acetate	Ethyl lactate	Ethyl caprylate	Ethyl acetate	Ethyl capronate	Ethyl caprylate	Hexil acetate
1	3,22	4,06	0,71	3,98	14,8	2,1	1,21	0,34
2	17,39	8,65	1,27	5,38	16,4	4,14	0,85	0,99
3	10,4	5,06	1,25	5,29	11,6	2,68	1,19	1,03
4	13,63	6,14	1,7	4,7	11,2	3,5	0,75	0,96
5	9,9	4,14	1,84	3,43	13,2	2,68	0,76	1,49
6	1,12	2,3	0,65	2,39	6,4	0,92	0,99	0,15
7	4	1,95	0,58	2,39	12,8	2,06	0,8	0,16

Along with these unsaturated esters, saturated carboxylic acids were also detected. They have no smell at all or have unpleasant tones. But the threshold of perception of these acids is low, so

they do not have a significant effect on the aromatic profile of rose table wines [3,4].

Butyl lactone was detected in all samples. It has very pleasant smell and appears to be the result of

yeast metabolism [2,7,10]. Its content varies from 1.1 to 1.73 mg/dm³.

Conclusions

Thus, the results of the research consist in a determining of a group of substances and their representatives that are responsible for the formation of aromatic profile of rose table wines. Among them there are isoamyl β -phenyl ethyl alcohol, hexanol, heptanol, octanol, nonanol, α -bysabolol, tyrozol, ethyl acetate, ethyl propionate, butyrate, isoamil acetate, hexyl acetate, ethyl caprylate, ethyl caprylate, β -phenil ethyl acetate, ethyl lactate and butyr lactone.

These results show directions for a development of the research. An impact of yeast races, fermentation conditions, grape variety and conditions of its cultivation on the formation of the aromatic profile of rose table wines have to be studied.

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VEGETABLE OILS EXTRACTION BY PRESSING OLEAGINOUS SEEDS: THE INFLUENCE FACTORS

ADRIAN-OVIDIU ARIȘANU*

Abstract: *On a worldwide scale, obtaining quality vegetable oils greatly depends on the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the raw materials, as well as on the extraction procedure. The issue of vegetable oils extraction from oleaginous raw materials is quite topical nowadays, being a major concern both for specialists, who are permanently working on finding solutions intended to improve this process (increasing extraction efficiency, reducing energy consumption, introducing various environmentally friendly technologies), but in the present situation, when the humanity is faced with a serious economic crisis, potential consumers seem to grow more and more concerned about this issue.*

Keywords: *parameters, temperature, mechanical oil expression, yield, hydraulic presses, screw presses.*

1. Introduction

Separation of oil from oilseeds is an important processing operation. The process employed has a direct effect on the quality and quantity of protein and oil obtained from the oilseeds. Basically, two methods are used for this purpose [3]. One is the solvent extraction method in which a solvent, when brought in contact with the preconditioned oilseed, dissolves the oil present in the seed and the separated mixture is later heated to evaporate the solvent and obtain the oil [6]. The method is most popular in North America and Europe, is highly efficient (over 98.5...99% oil recovery) and a single extractor can handle very large capacities (up to 4000 tonnes per day). The method, however, requires a large infrastructure with high initial cost and there is a fire and pollution hazard as it requires large quantities of highly flammable solvents [6].

The other method used involves mechanical oil expression. In this process, the preconditioned oilseed is passed through a screw press where a combination of high temperature and shear is used to crush the oilseed to release the oil [6]. The method is relatively less efficient as it recovers only 70...80% of the available oil, depending on the oilseed and pressure employed. Pretreatments and operating conditions determine the efficiency of the screw press but each pass can handle much smaller quantity of oilseeds (up to 1000 tonnes per day). Oilseed pressing involves very low initial and operating costs compared to the solvent method of oil extraction and is relatively free of any polluting or fire

hazardous substances [6]. This method is most widely used for oil expression in the developing countries or for high oil content seeds in combination with a solvent system [6].

2. Materials and methods

The oleaginous raw materials and numerous and most varied. Of more than 110 species of oleaginous plants, on the world market there are presently about 45, grouped in 15 important botanical families [3, 4, 7], namely: compositae (sunflower), cruciferae (rape), leguminous plants (soya), malvaceae (cotton), papaveraceae (poppy), rozaceae (almond tree, hazel tree), peduliaceae (sesame), vitaceae (grape seed), jugladaceae (nut tree), palmae (oil palm, coconut palm, palm kernel), foleaceae (olive tree), linaceae (flax), cucurbitaceae (pumpkin seeds), leufobiaceae (castor oil plant) and solanaceae (tomato seeds, tobacco seeds) [3].

Due to their particular importance, oleaginous plants are being grown worldwide, the extent of each culture depending on the geographical area. Thus, if on a worldwide scale the palm tree holds the top position among the oleaginous raw materials, with 29,3% of the world vegetable oil production, in Europe, sunflower is ranked first, with 36,2% of the oil production, being closely followed by rape, with a share of 32,1% [7]. In Romania, the mainly grown oleaginous plant is sunflower, with 78% of the domestic vegetable oil production [7]. As far as the areas under

cultivation are concerned, in 2001 Romania was ranked first among the EU member states; however, the average yield per hectare remained by approximately 14% lower than the means on record in the other states of the European Union.

In Romania, in order to separate the vegetable oil from oleaginous seeds, is used almost always, in industry practice, the combined process, namely the pressing of the oleaginous material, which enables an oil separation up to 80...85%, followed by solvent extraction, whereby the remaining oil is being separated [3].

The combined procedure (expression-solvent extraction) is applied in the processing of oleaginous raw materials with a minimum oil content of 30%. Raw materials with lower oil content are directly processed by solvent extraction, as the low yield of their expression does not justify the costs generated by this method [3, 4].

Depending on the characteristics of oleaginous seeds, the degree of equipment of the processing facilities and the desired extraction degree, there are 5 main categories of oleaginous material which can be subjected to extraction by pressing:

- oleaginous seeds as such;
- ground unshelled oleaginous seeds;
- ground unshelled but hydrothermally processed oleaginous seeds;
- ground shelled oleaginous seeds;
- ground shelled and hydrothermally processed oleaginous seeds.

Considering the above, we may note that the grinding of oleaginous seeds is an omnipresent operation in the vegetable oil processing technologies (except for the first situation, very rarely met in current industrial practice on account of the low quality of the obtained oil). As regards the hulling of the oleaginous seeds and the hydrothermal processing of the ground seeds, although these perceived as optional operations, both the quality of oil and that of the resulting seed meal, as well as the enhancement of extraction yields, greatly depend on their application.

After the grinding of the hulled oleaginous seeds and the hydrothermal processing of the resulting ground seeds, the technological process of vegetable oil extraction from oleiferous seeds continues with the pressing of the hydrothermally processed oleaginous material. For that purpose, the oleaginous material heated at temperatures comprised between 80 and 95 Celsius degrees, can be transferred from the hydrothermal processing system directly inside the feeding vat of the pressing equipment. The results of the experimental researches have pointed out that in this temperature range (80...95 Celsius degrees), a maximum extraction can be attained (fig. 1) and at the same time the obtained oil is of the highest quality, for which reason the ground oleaginous seeds are transferred from the hydrothermal processing system directly to the pressing equipment without any intermediate processing [1].

Fig. 1. Influence of the temperature of ground oleaginous seeds on oil extraction degree.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the pressing process (hydraulic presses).

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the pressing process (screw presses) [6].

Following the introduction of the oleaginous material into the pressing chamber (fig. 2, 3), the first thing that occurs is the separation of oil (over a short period of time) without any exterior

action, only through the effect of the gravitational field and of the pressure of material layers. This first phase unfolds as a sheer filtering process under the influence of a hydrostatic pressure. The actual pressing process is achieved through the action of an active organ (piston or screw), which initially achieves a compression of the oleaginous materials aimed at eliminating air pockets by evacuating the air existing between the particles of ground seeds. This is followed by the separation of the oil kept on the surface of the particles due to the surface forces of the molecular field, through the channels formed between the particles [2]. The increase in the pressing forces engenders a decrease in particle volume, which causes the oil to be eliminated from the particle capillaries, at the same time as the separation of the oil existing on the surface thereof. The increase in the pressure exerted on the ground oleaginous seeds needs to be gradual, so that the finely ground particles do not obstruct the capillaries thereby blocking oil evacuation.

When the space between the surfaces of two particles becomes so narrow that the oil film is subjected to the retention forces exerted by both particle surfaces, the oil cannot be eliminated anymore, the film breaks in several places, the surfaces hit one against the other and the so-called oilseed cakes are formed.

Considering the structure of the ground and thermally processed oleaginous material and the

manner in which oil extraction is achieved, the pressing may be defined as the physical process of partial separation, under the action exerted by outer forces, of the liquid phase (oil) from an heterogeneous solid-liquid mixture (ground oleaginous seeds). The essential requirement to be met by the materials to be put through the pressing process is that the skeleton of the solid substance of the phases system be compressible and that draining capillaries be formed, enabling the passing of the liquid phase.

3. Conclusions

Mechanical expression is the oldest method used for oil extraction from seeds. The seeds are placed between permeable barriers and mechanical pressure is increased by reducing the volume available for the seeds. This way oil is squeezed from the seeds. In practice, this operation can take two shapes: a hydraulic, uni-axial press or a screw press (also called extruder or expeller).

The advantages of a screw press compared to a hydraulic press are its slightly higher yield and its continuous mode of operation. Mechanical expression results in high quality oil, but has a relatively low yield. Generally it is only used for smaller capacity plants, speciality products, or as a pre-press operation in a large scale solvent extraction plant.

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INNOVATIVE IDEAS FOR THE OPTIMIZATION OF THE POTATO SORTING PROCESS

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Abstract: *Potato sorting is an operation that is done mainly through mechanical methods. Modern systems for potato sorting are based on the separation by optical methods. Classic methods, but also modern methods for potato sorting can be optimized by different means. Innovations may constitute even some commonplace ideas, derived from different areas and their principle may be very useful in the identification of some perfectible elements at the researched systems. Qualitative sorting has the role of improving the properties of the agricultural products that will finally become food products. That's why the methods by which it can be done must be observed and permanently optimized.*

Keywords: *potato sorting, methods, innovations.*

1. Introduction

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum L*) is one of the most important plants with alimentary, industrial and fodder use. The chemical composition of potato tubers includes: starch 13...16 %, proteins 0,8...4,9 %, vitamins – mainly vitamin C, mineral salts in very varied proportions, but also some toxic alkaloids, like solanine [2].

Originating from the South America, potato contains more than 500 species, from which 38 are cultivated [2].

Potato is very exigent regarding the requirements for the weather and soil. *Parmetier* said: *The production at potato is always proportional with the care that it is conferred* [1].

Due to the large ecological plasticity, potato is found nowadays cultivated all over the Globe [3].

There is an optimal regarding the conditions of weather and soil, as the altitude and latitude. The humidity and the temperature are the most important parameters in the technology of cultivation for the potato [3].

As the palette of industrial products acquired by potatoes is very large, the industrial potato does not include only the tubers extracted after potato sorting. Potato contributes to the control of herbs and it is a good precursory for other cereals [2].

Potato is an annual plant that multiplies by tubers and in the creation of potato breeds, it is used the potato semen [2].

After their use, potatoes may be:

- potatoes for direct consumption: for extra-early and early use, for summer and autumn – winter use;
- potatoes for the food industry: dry products (flour, dehydrated, flakes, semolina), roasted products (chips, *pommes frites*, crisps) and derived products (salads, canes);
- industrial potatoes for starch and alcohol: starch (dextrin, dextrose), alcohol;
- fodder potatoes;
- seed potatoes [2].

The potato's productivity is increased:

- early breeds reach a production of 10...16 tones/ hectare;
- half-early breeds and half-late breeds produce 15...30 tones/ hectare;
- late breeds up to 30 tones/ hectare [2].

The potatoes may have different shapes:

- round;
- oval or full - oval;
- long;
- shapes that are between these [3].

Dependent on the size, potato tubers may be:

- large tubers: above 120 g;
- medium tubers: 80...120g;
- small tubers: 40...80 g;
- very small tubers: less than 40 g [3].

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2. Methods

The present paper aims to:

- delimitate the main characteristics and elements of the potato sorting technique;
- identify some distinct domains where the above principles may be applied and to take over some information, with the aim of optimizing some aspects from the potato sorting process (author).

Although during the potato harvest process, a series of measures are taken so that finally load in the means of transport only whole tubers, in the harvested mass, there are also some foreign bodies: clods of soil, rocks, herbs, ill tubers or damaged ones, that cannot be used for planting or consumption. All these foreign bodies from the potato mass are eliminated through the sorting process [4].

The harvesting and the conditioning of the potatoes have to be done in a continuous technological flow, as for example: the material from the harvest machines must be passed through the installation for the separation of the foreign bodies from potatoes, simultaneously with the harvesting and in the case of the seed potatoes supplementary through the sizing machine [1].

The harvesting is done in the same technological flow with the conditioning, so a great amount of mechanical and working forces are being used [1].

Example of a technological flow for sorting and conditioning: from the installation for the separation of the foreign bodies from potatoes, the potatoes are loaded in special trucks; at the centers of processing, the qualitative and quantitative reception is done (the mass determination, the determination of the percent of foreign bodies and the percent of tubers with mechanical injuries or ill potatoes) [1].

The sorting is the operation of separating products on categories, after some criteria regarding their exterior aspect as the degree of damage, the color, the shape, the health and other characteristics [4].

The potato sorting starts from the field, where after the harvesting, it is done a pre-sorting and the products that present visible departures from the requested quality are eliminated and continues even at the processing places [4].

Some authors [4] found that the sorting is of two categories:

- general sorting;
- selective sorting.

The general sorting (Fig. 1) refers to the examination of each product and passing it in to a certain category. This operation is partially mechanized, by using some special tables, or some transporters for the products or for the package and some chamfers or deflector panels. This method has the advantage of a precise separation, but asks for a lot of manual work, large spaces to work and the production is relatively low [4].

The products that arrive on the transporters (1) are being examined by workers placed at the work places (2) and deposited in the lateral devices (3), for the corresponding specimens and in the chamfer (4) for the ones that do not correspond. For the delimitation of the chamfers, there are mounted some side walls (5) [4].

Fig. 1 The general sorting machine [4]

There are also automatized machines for the general sorting (e.g. sorting by color, sorting with photoelectrical cells) [4].

The functioning of the photoelectrical machines for sorting is based on the fact that the passing of a product with a different color with of the one of the paravane is detected by the photocells that produce an electrical impulse. This impulse is amplified and commands for the functioning of the injector, that deviates the products with an air jet. Instead, the products that have the same color with the ones of the paravane pass by the front of the photocells and no impulse is initiated [4].

The selective sorting is done by extracting from the mass of products the specimens that do not correspond qualitatively and if they are in the great majority, by removing the corresponding ones [4].

It can be seen that the main part of the sorting machines is the transporter belt. From this, the idea can be expanded, as in the case of other types of transporters used in the industry, as the transporters for the ballast (author).

No doubt that this kind of ideas could appear continuously, but the goal is the identifying of as many similitudes as possible, even at the beginning they seem to lack of importance, for the identification of as many points in the sorting flow that can be the subject of some optimizations (author).

3. Results and Discussions

From the analysis of the main systems for potato sorting, that are the mechanical ones (see *the general sorting machine*) and optical ones (see *the photoelectrical machines*), there were proposed the following areas from where to get some inspiring ideas for the optimization of the process:

- detectors for the gases;
- fire detectors;
- the sorting of fish;
- the sorting of the ballast (author).

Another proposal that could contribute to the optimization of the sorting process is the analyzing some theorems of the mechanics, as the theorem of the mechanical impulse and the aero dynamical resistance (author).

The gases and the fire detectors may be adjusted and placed on a potato sorting flow, as to identify some potato specimens that are ill or damaged and emanate gases like carbon dioxide (CO_2), ammonia (NH_3), sulfurized hydrogen (H_2S) or even small amount of heat (author).

From the gas detectors, a special class - Handheld Infrared Carbon Dioxide Gas Detector RHB Series (Fig. 2) manages to detect the carbon dioxide (CO_2), the carbon monoxide (CO), the ammonia (NH_3) or the sulfurized hydrogen (H_2S) [8].

Fig 2. Special gas detector [7]

The fire detectors are composed mainly by:

- fire detectors;
- analyzer for the received signal;
- device for alarming;
- energy source [10].

The sorting of fish by size can be done:

- passively, by using installations with counter-flow and grates with different sizes of the spaces between the wands;
- actively, by the used of some mechanized installations, with grates or with cylinders [11].

In the case of potato sorting, this idea may be very useful, as to identify some new methods for sorting the potatoes in the technological flow, but both as a supplementary method, for a better separation, after the process is done (author).

The sorting of ballast is a process that is very close as a manner of evolving with the one of potato sorting (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 The sorting of ballast (lateral view) [9]

It can be seen (Fig. 3) that the machines for the sorting of ballast resemble very much with the ones for potato sorting. By observing this process closely, some ideas could appear regarding the way in which the processes take place (author).

The great difference between the two sorting types (potatoes and ballast) is the mass and the shape of the material that is being sorted (author).

The general theorems of mechanics represent an unitary system of arguable theorems on the basis of mechanic's principles. They particularize functional relations between dynamic physical measures and are useful in the description of the mechanical behavior of mechanical systems [5].

The theorem of impulse expresses the relation between the force that acts upon the material point and the variation in time of its impulse. The material point has a mass and it is considered as being in move in a inertial system and its position is conferred by a position vector, in a Cartesian system. The force is the resultant of all the forces that operate simultaneously upon the material point at one moment [5].

Taking into account that the potato sorting is an operation that implies the action of some forces and the potato is moving continuous on it, this theorem may be useful in studying closely the kinematics of the potato on the sorter, but also other phenomenon (author).

The main role of an aero dynamical system is the creation of a larger carrying force, having also a resistance at advance as smaller as possible[6]. The main aspect in the case of this system is that the moving of the potato on the sorting machine would be facilitated (author).

Conclusions

The main element of the mechanical sorting machines is the transporter belt. There may be taken some useful information from other areas like the sorting of ballast and not only with the goal of optimizing some punctual aspects in the technological flow of potato sorting (author).

The mechanic's theorems may be very useful in the optimization of the potato's kinematics on the sorting machine, having into account that the potatoes move continuously on the sorter (author).

Regarding the biochemical changes of the harvested and sorted potatoes, an interesting idea would be the use of some special sensors for the detection of the gases that they emanate in the case of damage or when they suffer from some diseases (author).

Innovative ideas could appear continuously, but it is important to select the ones that have a real

impact upon the finding of some aspects, ideas and practical guides as to optimize the potato sorting (author).

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RESEARCH IR SPECTRA PECTINS AND GELS ON THEIR BASIS

I. KRAPYVNYTSKA, D. PRASOL, F. PERTCEVOI, T. KUZNETSOVA

Abstract: Studied the IR-spectra high-ester (CE = 62 - 66%) and of low-ester (CE = 31 - 36%) apple pectin in the solid phase. In order to detect differences in the structure formation of these pectins studied the IR spectra of films of dry gels (system pectin-sugarcitric acid). Comparison of the obtained IR spectra of dried gels from high-ester and low-ester apple pectins showed that for the first mentioned pectin formed a solid gel structure.

Keywords: pectin, degree of esterification, structure formation, film of gel, IR-spectra.

1. Introduction

In recent years, worldwide production of pectin increased almost twice. Unique properties of pectin as a food and biological additives resulted in his special role in the economy of developed countries. Pectin is widely used in various sectors of the food industry as gel former, stabilizer, thickener and emulsifier [1, 2, 3]. Accordingly, the actual development pectin industry in Ukraine is a complex of theoretical and experimental studies to the scientific basis and the development of modern, highly efficient technologies pectin and products on pectin basis [4].

During the acid extraction of fruits and vegetables (beets, apples, citrus) are excluded pectins, which constitute a group of commercial pectin. For these pectins are usually used marc citrus and apples - a byproduct in obtaining juice and beet pulp - waste of sugar from sugar beets. For apple and citrus pectins characterized by alternating linear 1, 4 - linked chains α , D - galacturonan and extensive area, which contains most of the neutral polysaccharides. These pectins differ in molecular weight and content of rhamnose, arabinose, galactose and other monosaccharides.

Physicochemical properties of commercial pectins depend on their molecular weight and degree of esterification [5]. The degree of esterification is determined by the number of moles of methanol per 100 mol of galacturonic acid. Pectins with high degree of esterification containing more than 50% esterified galacturonan residues. Low-ester pectins contain less than 50% esterified residues. Both groups of pectin polysaccharides form a gels, but under different conditions: for low-ester pectin requires low values of pH or the presence of calcium ions, and

for high-ester pectin gel formation occurs by hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions.

2. Experimental part

The aim of our work was to investigate the IR-spectra of dry films of pectin gels with different degrees of esterification and identifying differences in the structure formation of its pectins.

Terms of characteristic absorption bands of IR-spectra gel formers and their intensity determined by the nature of atomic groups that are part of macromolecules and their location relative to each other [6]. If the composition of the macromolecules are ionic group, while a characteristic absorption band depends on the nature and degree of oxidation of low molecular counterions. IR-spectra can provide additional information on possible interactions of macromolecules with low molecular weight additives to form associates. Spectra analysis also provides information on how these atomic groups of macromolecules involved in molecular interactions, if sufficiently strong effect on the oscillation frequency of connections.

Research pectins by IR-spectroscopy were started much later than other polysaccharides. The considered only the most intense and characteristic bands. It is possible to identify the IR spectra pectin in food products and to distinguish them from other gel formers. Later research began IR-spectra of pectin derivatives obtained by oxidation of pectin and stitching his chains [7, 8].

Compared to the numerous studies of polysaccharides works connect with infrared spectroscopy of pectins bit. This is due to the complexity of the allocation of these substances

in a state close to the native and imperfect methods of preparing samples for analysis.

The first phase of work we have obtained IR-spectra high-ester (CE = 62 - 66%) and of low-ester (CE = 31 - 36%) of apple pectin in crystalline state (solid phase). Samples of pectin are homogenized with optically pure dry potassium bromide. As a result, pressing the mixture obtained pills size 22×5 mm and weighing 150 mg. Spectra were relatively potassium bromide in the region from 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} on a spectrophotometer with Fourier transformation of TENSOR 27. In such spectrophotometers used polychromatic radiation

and calculated spectrum in a given frequency range by Fourier conversion output.

3. Results and discussion

The obtained IR-spectra of pectins are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Table 1 shows the results of the analysis obtained IR-spectra of high-ester and low-ester apple pectins in the solid phase.

The second phase of work, we investigated the IR-spectra of gels on the basis of high-ester and low-ester apple pectins, compounding the composition of which is given in Table. 2.

Figure 1. IR-spectra of dry high-ester apple pectin

Figure 2. IR-spectra of dry low-ester apple pectin

Table 1. The results of IR-spectra of high-ester and low-ester apple pectin in the solid phase

High-ester apple pectin		Low-ester apple pectin		The assignment of bands	Conclusions
Areas of peaks, cm ⁻¹	Skipping, %	Areas of peaks, cm ⁻¹	Skipping, %		
3389,37	10	3411,86	14	stretching vibrations of OH-related H-bond	strong broad peak, characteristic of carbohydrates
2942,21	72	2944,26	81	covalent bond stretching vibrations of C-H (condition C - sp ³ hybridization)	at methylation of carboxyl group absorption increases
2895,87	79	2897,62	83		
2837,00	84	2838,02	87		
1751,47	70	1754,99	85	stretching vibrations of carbonyl C = O ester groups	for high-ester pectin absorption increases due to more difficult-essential groups
1631,26	70	1628,56	57	stretching vibrations of COO ⁻	for low-ester pectin absorption more due to dissociation is not methylated carboxyl groups
1442,18 – 1238,34	65	1494,72 – 1272,99	80 – 75	internal deformation vibrations of methyl group-CH ₃ ; stretching vibrations of air the C-O-C.	for high-ester pectin absorption increases due to more difficult-essential groups
1104,46	39	1133,62	60	stretching vibrations of the C-C and C-O piranoznych cycles and C-O-C ether bridges.	for high-ester pectin absorption more due to more difficult-essential groups
1051,40	27	1052,55	50		
1012,56	33	999,4	55		
920,77	69	948,42	82	pendulum oscillations in hard-CH ₃ ester groups	for high-ester pectin absorption more due to more difficult-essential groups

Table 2. Composition of pectin gels

raw	Mass fraction of dry substances, %	Total cost of raw materials taking into account losses in the technological process, 100 g	
		In nature	In solids
Apple pectin	92,00	1,00	0,92
Sugar	99,85	65,00	64,90
Citric	91,20	0,80	0,73
Water		33,20	-
Total		100,00	66,55

Difficulty applying IR-spectroscopy to study gels is that the presence of significant amounts of water leads to an overlap of nearly all the characteristic bands of macromolecules. Therefore, IR-spectroscopy gel formers preferred method of removing the spectra in the form of films [9]. This is due to the fact that the manufacture of polymer films can not be destruction, and in the spectra due to the homogeneity of the samples are usually not observed violations by the uneven distribution of compounds.

For film samples pectin gel thin layer deposited on a plastic base and dried at $20 \pm 1,0$ ° C in a desiccators. The dried film is well shot with the basics. Spectra were relatively potassium bromide in the region from 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} on a spectrophotometer with Fourier transformation of TENSOR 27.

In Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 shows the IR-spectra of films of gels based on high-ester and low-ester apple pectin taken relatively pure pectin.

Figure 3. IR spectrum of the gel from high-ester apple pectin

Figure 4. IR spectrum of the gel-based low-ester apple pectin

When comparing the absorption peaks within $3366,81\text{ cm}^{-1} - 3240,12\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for high-ester pectin and $3426,31\text{ cm}^{-1} - 3272,52\text{ cm}^{-1}$ - of low-ester pectin, it is clear that the first of these peaks shifted low-frequency region. These peaks correspond to vibrations of free hydroxyl groups. For both samples pectin compared with the frequency of oscillation of free hydroxyl groups, these peaks are shifted in the low-frequency region. This is due to the participation of hydroxyls in the system of H-bonds.

For high-ester pectin is greater absorption intensity and frequency lower. This suggests an increase in the strength of H-bonds in comparison with the model based of low-ester pectin.

The second area of peak absorption for high-ester pectin is between $1689.70\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1528.42\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and for low-ester pectin – $1687.04\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1524.96\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Maximum absorption falls to 1618.06 cm^{-1} for the sample on the basis of high-ester pectin and 1620.43 cm^{-1} – sample of low-ester pectin. Such pikes absorption corresponding fluctuations dissociated carboxyl groups COO^- . Acquisitions in the above areas for samples from both pectins close.

Comparison of IR-spectra obtained films gels (system pectin-sugar-citric acid) on the basis of high-ester and low-ester pectins showed that for the first mentioned pectin produced more robust gel structure.

Conclusions

Studied the infrared spectra high-ester (CE = 62 - 66%) and low-ester (CE = 31 - 36%) of apple pectin in the solid phase.

Studied the infrared spectra of dry films jelly pectin with different degrees of esterification to detect differences in the structure formation of pectin.

Found that gel (pectin-sugar-citric acid) from high-ester apple pectin produced more robust structure compared with the gel-based of low apple pectin.

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LOW TEMPERATURE EXTRACTION OF PLANTS BY LIQUIFICATE GASES WASTE OF CHOKEBERRY FRUITS (*Aronia melanocarpa* (Michx) Elliott.)

P. MERDZHANOV, M. ANGELOV-ROMOVA, N. NENOV, M. ZLATANOV, G. ANTOV, T. ATANASOV, P. DENEV, A. STOYANOVA

Abstract: The lipid composition from waste of chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa* (Michx) Elliott.) extraction with freon134a (1,1,1,2-tetrafluorethane) and with freon 134a+acetone was analyzed using GC and HPLC. The main components in the triacylglycerol fractions were linoleic (47.8 – 57.2%), oleic (26.4 – 28.4%) and palmitic (11.0 – 15.5%) acids. β -Tocopherol (59.3 – 61.4%) predominated in the tocopherol fractions, and β -sitosterol (74.3%) – in the sterol fraction.

Keywords: waste of aronia fruits, lipid composition.

1. Introduction

Aronia (*Aronia melanocarpa* (Michx) Elliott.), family *Rosaceae* originates from the eastern parts of North America. It is industrially cultivated in many European countries as an industrial crop. The chokeberries are good raw material for the production of various beverages including juices, nectars, syrups, jellies, jams, tea, wines and liquors [11].

The berries contain anthocyanins, flavonols, valuable minerals, vitamins and dietary fibres [11, 12, 15, 19, 20, 22].

Chokeberries have a long traditional use in folk medicine. Among the health benefits of chokeberries are: inhibition of cancer cell proliferation, antimutagenic effect, hepatoprotective effect, cardioprotective effect and antidiabetes effect [21].

Data about the chemical composition of the lipid fraction of chokeberries fruits are scarce. In the lipid fraction of the fruits from the chokeberries, growing in Bulgaria Antova [2] and Zlatanov [24] have been identified oleic (21.4%), linoleic (71.1%) and palmitic acid (5.1%). In the lipid fraction incorporates phospholipids (2.8%), mainly phosphatidylinositol (29.8%); sterols (1.2%), mainly β -sitosterol (89.8%) and tocopherols (55.5 mg/kg), mainly α -tocopherol (70.6%). In our previous paper we established in the lipid fraction from the waste the many acids, but in different quality - linoleic (39.7%), oleic (30.7%) and palmitic (19.8%) acids. The main components in the tocopherol fraction were β -tocopherol (59.7%) and β -sitosterol (82.6%) and campesterol (6.4%) – in the sterol fraction [1].

In the lipid fraction investigated by Anwar et al., [3] the prevailing fatty components were linoleic (27.9%), oleic (61.90%) and palmitic acids (3.2%), as well as sterols mainly β -sitosterol (66.0%), Δ^5 -avenasterol (18.0%) and campesterol (5.0%).

Currently in many countries medical plants are processed by extraction with liquefied gases (CO_2 , air, freon 134a and other). The produced extracts are harmless that's why they can be widely used in food and flavour industry, cosmetics and medicine. The usage of liquefied gases overcomes the drawbacks of installations working with volatile polar and apolar solvents [13].

The aim of present study is producing of waste of chokeberry by using freon 134a and mix of freon 134a and acetone in laboratory installation and determination of their chemical composition and characteristics for possible application in natural food product.

2. Materials and Methods

Samples. The plant material was aronia fruit waste, which was dried at room temperature.

The moisture content (7.9%) was determined by drying up to constant weight, at 105°C (Russian Pharmacopoeia, 1990).

The used solvent 1,1,1,2 tetrafluorethane (freon 134a) is apolar with relative permittivity at 20°C and 100 kHz 1.013, dipole moment 2.060 Debay and polarization 13.8 cm³/mol. Its dynamic viscosity and surface tension at 20°C are small, 198 $\mu\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ and 8 mN/m, respectively, which allows easier penetration into plant cells and

benefits extraction of cells associated compounds. Its pressure at 20°C is 0.57 MPa, which allows the extraction process to be carried out at acceptable pressures from 0.2 to 0.7 MPa. Its specific heat of vaporization at the applied thermal regime is low (about 200 kJ/kg), which determines small energy consumption for extraction process. The solvent is also chemically inert and it is well compatible with copper and carbon steel. The influence of freon134a on the Green House Effect, with coefficient HGWP = 0.285, and its higher price are its major disadvantages.

The other solvent is acetone.

Extraction. The air-waste are ground separately in an attrition mill to a size of 0.15 – 0.25 mm and extracted in laboratory scale 1 l volume extractor using subcritical liquefied gas co-extraction. The used solvent was mixture of liquefied gas tetrafluoroethane and acetone in proportion (tetrafluoroethane : acetone 10:1) for total amount of acetone of 49 g. The weight of sample was 280 g. The extraction temperature was 25 – 30°C and absolute extraction pressure was 0.70 – 0.80 MPa. The extraction process featured triple exchange of solvent with duration of each stage of 30 min. Total duration of extraction process was 90 min.

The solvents was partly removed in a rotary vacuum evaporator, the residue was transferred to a pre-weighed glass vessel and the rest of the solvent was removed under stream of nitrogen to a constant weight, in order to determine the oil content [6].

Fatty acids. The total fatty acid composition of the oil was determined by GC after transmethylation of the respective sample with 2N methanolic KOH at 50°C according to Christie [4]. Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were purified by TLC on 20 cm x 20 cm plates covered with 0.2 mm Silica gel 60 G layer (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) with mobile phase n-hexane:acetone, 100 : 8 (by volume).

Determination was performed on a gas chromatograph equipped with a 30 m x 0.25 mm x 25 µm (I.D.) capillary EC 30-Wax column (Hewlett Packard GmbH, Vienna, Austria) and a flame ionization detector. The column temperature was programmed from 130°C (hold 1 min), at 6.5°C/min to 170 °C, at 3°C/min to 215°C (hold 9 min), at 40°C/min to 230°C (hold 1 min); injector were 270°C and detector temperatures were 280°C Hydrogen was the carrier gas at a flow rate 0.8 ml/min; split was 50:1.

Identification was performed by comparison of retention times with those of a standard mixture of FAME subjected to GC under identical experimental conditions [5, 7].

Sterols. Unsaponifiables were determined by weight after saponification of the lipid fraction and extraction with hexane [10]. The unsaponifiable matters (100 mg, precisely measured) was applied on 20 cm x 20 cm glass plates (ca. 1 mm thick Silica gel G layer) and developed with n-hexane acetone, 100 : 8 (by volume). Free sterols ($R_f = 0.4$) were detected under UV light by spraying the edges of each plate with 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein, they were then scraped, transferred to small glass columns and eluted with diethyl ether. The solvent was evaporated under a stream of nitrogen and the residue was weighed in small glass containers to a constant weight. Sterol composition was determined by GC using HP 5890 gas chromatograph (Hewlett Packard GmbH, Vienna, Austria) equipped with a 25 m x 0.25 mm DB – 5 capillary column (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara CA, USA) and a flame ionization detector.

Temperature gradient was from 90°C (hold 2 min) up to 290°C at a rate 15°C/min and then up to 310°C at a rate of 4°C/min (hold 10 min); the injector temperature was 300°C and the detector temperature was 320°C. Hydrogen was used as carrier gas at a flow rate 0.8 ml/min; split 50 : 1.

Identification was confirmed by comparison of retention times with those of a standard mixture of sterols [9].

Tocopherols. Tocopherols were determined directly in the oil by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) by a Merck-Hitachi (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) unit equipped with a 250 mm x 4 mm Nucleosil Si 50-5 column (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and a fluorescent detector Merck-Hitachi F 1000. The operating conditions were as follows: mobile phase n-hexane : dioxan, 96 : 4 (by volume), flow rate 1.0 ml/min, excitation 295 nm, emission 330 nm. 20 µl 1% solution of crude oil were injected.

Tocopherols were identified by comparing the retention times to those of authentic individual pure tocopherols. The tocopherol content was calculated on the base of tocopherol peak areas in the sample vs. tocopherol peak area of the standard tocopherol solution [8].

2. Results and Discussions

The lipid fractions were 0.07% in the extract with freon 134a and 0.27% in extract with mixture freon 134a+acetone. As seen the results for the yields of extracts are comparable with literature data are almost very small with these for the lipid fraction obtained by traditional solvents.

The extracts are odorless viscous products with amber color.

The fatty acid composition is presented in Table 1. Data show that 11 fatty acids were detected, constituting 100% of the total oil content.

The main fatty acids in lipid fraction were oleic, linoleic and palmitic acids. In the extracts, according to data from the literature are identified as predominating the same three fatty acids, but in different quantities, which could be explained by the influence of the origin of the raw.

Table 1. Fatty acid composition, % (w/w).

№	Fatty acids	Extract with freon 134a	Extract with freon 134a+acetone
1.	C _{12:0} Lauric	1.6	0.9
2.	C _{14:0} Myristic	1.1	0.7
3.	C _{16:0} Palmitic	15.5	11.0
4.	C _{16:1} Palmitoleic	0.4	0.2
5.	C _{17:0} Margaric	0.2	0.2
6.	C _{18:0} Stearic	2.8	1.2
7.	C _{18:1} Oleic	28.4	26.4
8.	C _{18:2} Linoleic	47.8	57.2
9.	C _{18:3} Linolenic	1.1	0.9
10.	C _{20:0} Arachidic	0.9	1.1
11.	C _{20:1} Gadoleic	0.2	0.2

The correlation unsaturated : saturated fatty acids was 77.9 : 22.1 in the extract with freon 134a and 84.9 : 15.1 in extract with freon 134a +acetone.

Their distribution profiles are presented on Figures 1 and 2. Palmitic acid predominated in the fraction of saturated fatty acids and oleic and linoleic were predominant among the unsaturated acids.

Fig. 1. Distribution of fatty acids in extract with freon 134a.

1 - Saturated acids (22.1%);
2 - Monounsaturated acids (29.0%);
3 - Polyunsaturated acids (48.9%).

Fig. 2. Distribution of fatty acids in extract with freon 134a+acetone.

1 - Saturated acids (15.1%);
2 - Monounsaturated acids (26.8%);
3 - Polyunsaturated acids (58.1%).

Regarding the individual presence of oleic and linoleic acid, the oil from waste of chokeberries was similar to the oils from other nontraditional

materials such as grape seeds, watermelon, tobacco and poppy seeds (Popov and Ilinov, 1986; Shterbakov, 1963). In lipid fractions form waste of aronia was found to contain very high

amounts of the saturated palmitic acid (11.0 – 15.5%), which comes close to the levels in other oils, like olive oil (7.5 - 20.0%) and corn oil (8.0 – 19.0%) [14].

Sterols are present in the so called non-saponificated part from the lipid fraction and in the extract with freon 134a its not determined.

By extraction with freon 134a+acetone their content in non- saponificated part is 13.7% and the total content in the extract was found to be 2.9%. The individual sterol composition is presented in Table 2. β -sitosterol predominated in

the sterol fraction. It is obvious from the data, that regarding its sterol content and composition, extract with freon 134a from waste of chokeberries was similar to the findings for lipid fraction with hexane from waste of aronia fruits [1], lipid fraction from the fruits of the *Apiaceae* family [23].

Table 2. Sterol composition, % (w/w).

№	Sterols	Extract with freon 134a+acetone
1.	Cholesterol	-*
2.	Campesterol	3.1
3.	Stigmasterol	3.8
4.	β - Sitosterol	74.3
5.	Δ^5 - Avenasterol	8.3
6.	Δ^7 - Stigmasterol	3.3
7.	Δ^7 - Avenasterol	7.2

* not detected

The total content of tocopherols in the lipid fraction was comparatively higher – 1530 mg/kg for extract with freon 134a and 1287 mg/kg for extract with freon 134a+acetone. The tocopherol and tocotrienol composition are presented in Table 3. The β -tocopherol predominated in the extracts, followed by γ -tocopherol and α -tocopherol. Regarding the low content of γ -

tocopherol the examined extracts proved superior to a number of common food oils, for example – corn oil (50.0 – 62.0%) and soya oil (60.0 – 85.0%), thus showing similarity to some non-traditional oils, such as pyrene oils of morello (93.1%) and apricot (96.0%) [16, 17].

Table 3. Tocopherol composition, % (w/w).

№	Tocopherols and tocotrienol	Extract with freon 134a	Extract with freon 134a+acetone
1.	α -Tocopherol	19.1	10.2
2.	α -Tocotrienol	0.7	-
3.	β -Tocopherol	61.4	59.3
4.	β -Tocotienol	-*	4.3
5.	γ -Tocopherol	18.8	21.4
6.	δ -Tocopherol	-	4.8

* not detected

Conclusion

For the first time in Bulgaria new extracts from waste of chokeberries (*Aronia melanocarpa* (Michx) Elliott.) were produced by extraction with liquefied gases - freon 134a and freon 134a+acetone. The yield of produced extracts was small, but their chemical composition was interesting. The extracts from waste of

chokeberries can be used as a non-traditional material rich in biologically active substances as oleic and linoleic acids, β -sitosterol and β -tocopherol for an additive in fodder mixtures in order to enrich them with valuable nutrients.

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EXISTENT AND PROPOSED SYSTEMS FOR POTATO SORTING

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Abstract: *The potato sorting machines can be classified after several criteria, as their destination, their means of activating, the place where they can be placed, but especially having regard of the active organs used at the sorting process. The present paper has the role of synthesizing the way of construction and functioning of the potato sorting machines and to propose elements or systems intended to contribute to the improvement of the technical parameters of the sorting process and both the sorting machines. The most important parameters of the potato sorting process are the separation of the foreign bodies and the reduction of the degree of bruising at the potatoes from the final mass.*

Keywords: *sorting, process, machines.*

1. Introduction

The potato sorting is a complex operation, having the role of eliminating all that is not a potato tuber. The elimination of the rocks, soil clods and of the particles of vegetables is done mechanically and the elimination of the ill or damaged tubers is done manually [1].

As some authors found, potatoes are agricultural products that are sorted in two phases [2].

The first phase, which is done after the harvesting process, consists on eliminating the remainders of soil, haulms, herbs, the sorting and the loading of the potatoes in the means of transport. These operations are done before storing and are very important, because they can prevent or reduce the losses at the storing process [2].

The first phase is done in the field or at the storing places, with isolated machines, or in some points or centers of sorting, where there are used the potatoes harvested from three to four machines [3].

The second phase consists on sizing, washing, drying, the elimination of unconditioned tubers and packaging. For the seed potatoes, this phase consists only of a strict control. The second phase includes some operations that are done on a technological flow that gathers all the range of necessary machines [3].

Because of the technological processing of potatoes, the manual work is being reduced. The machines are arranged in the order in which operations take place and there are being used transporter belts [1].

The sorting machines do the operation in cause after the linear dimensions of potatoes (length, width, thickness), on active organs with appropriate shapes [2].

The potato sorting machines are composed of some mechanisms that execute the following main operations:

- potato sorting;
- the elimination of foreign bodies;
- the selection of altered or damaged tubers [2].

There are also machines that do other operations like the loading of potatoes on the active organ, the transport of the fractions of sorted potatoes or the packing of the sorted potatoes [2].

Potatoes are being classified after the dimensions in ordinary potatoes and selected potatoes and the value of the size for each category are indicated in the standards that are specific for each country [1].

For example, in Romania, the selected potatoes are classified in four fractions:

- large potatoes: above 80 mm;
- seed potatoes I: 60...80 mm;
- seed potatoes II: 35...60 mm;
- small potatoes: less than 35 mm [1].

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2. Methods

Potato sorting machines are complex equipment that contains different devices that can be used to eliminate from the harvested mass of potatoes the great majority of foreign bodies, including the altered, ill or damaged potatoes. These machines have as main parts transporter belts and different active organs that effectuate the separation of adequate potatoes from the rest of the foreign bodies (author).

On the basis of knowing the means of construction and functioning of the main parts of these sorting machines, there may be identified some perfectible elements and by case, there may be adjusted some components of the known equipment or there may be conceptualized other systems or machines that can do the potato sorting process (author).

One classification [2] of the potato sorting machines situates them after:

- the destination: simple and combined machines;
- the means of activating: manual and mechanical machines;
- the place where they can be placed: mobile, stationary and half-stationary machines;
- the active organs used at the sorting process: machines with rolls, machines with belts and transporters, machines with vibratory sieves and machines with rotary sieves.

Simple sorting machines are used at the sorting in the field, at the potato stores they can partially mechanize the operations of loading and unloading [2].

Combined machines have besides the simple machines, one hopper for loading potatoes and that facilitates the operations of both loading and unloading. Mobile machines have a small capacity and are used at the sorting in the field. Stationary machines are used at large potato stores and the half-stationary ones in the case of some occasional displacements [2].

The most important classification regarding technological aspects is the one after the active organs. Each potato sorting machine has its own constructive characteristics and active organs placed at different points as transporter belts, surfaces for the control of tubers, therefore a strict analysis would mean to enumerate all the machines and mentioning the characteristics for each other [2].

Having regard of the information mentioned above, it is important to know this mean of classification, because at the great majority of

potato sorting machines, there are used active organs, so the basic characteristics may be extrapolated and analyzed in detail at the researched systems (author).

Sorting machines with rolls and transporters - belts (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) are composed mainly by:

- loading elevator;
- sorting surface with rolls or belts;
- elevators for unloading the large, medium and small fractions;
- cadre, actuation and rolling systems [2].

Fig. 1 Sorting machine with rolls [2]

Fig. 2 Sorting machine with belts [2]

The sorting machines with sieves may have as active organs beveled or oscillating sieves that can do longitudinal or transversal moves. The number of sieves is in correlation with the number of fractions in which potatoes are being sorted [2].

For example, the potato sorting machine TB – 26 (Fig. 3) is composed by:

- loading elevator;
- active organ for sorting;
- elevator for unloading;
- transporter for the sorted potatoes;
- cadre, actuation and rolling systems [2].

Fig. 3 Potato sorting machine TB – 26 [2]

Fig. 4 Rotary sorting machine [2]

The machines with rotary sieves (Fig. 4) contain a space for loading potatoes on the transporter. Between the wands of the loading cadre there are shaken down the particles of soil and the potatoes fall in the sectors of the rolling transporter [2].

Observations

These constructive types of potato sorting machines are relatively simple. The separation is done by mechanical methods (author).

The construction of these machines consists on few mechanisms and their productivity is also relatively reduced (author).

These machines produce damage at the sorted potatoes, due to the mechanical shocks of the potato tubers in contact with the active organs (author).

The construction and functioning of these machines is useful in the better understanding of the sorting process of potatoes, because these principles of construction and functioning are also found at complex equipment for potato sorting (author).

As to realize some proposals for the optimizing of some constructive and functional parameters at the sorting installations, there should be done several experimental researches upon different constructive types of this sort of machines. The first phase of this study is the observation of the main components of a potato sorting machine.

The potato sorting machine from the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet (NIRDPSB) from Brasov (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6) is composed by the following:

- reception hopper;
- installation for the sorting of foreign bodies;
- elevator band for transport;
- inspection table;
- installation of calibration with sieves;
- transporter belts [3].

Fig. 5 Inspection table from NIRDPSB Brasov

Fig. 6 Calibration sieves from NIRDPSB Brasov

The main characteristics of the potato sorting machines with transporters are:

- the productivity;
- the number of fractions;
- the necessary electrical power;
- the dimensions of the sorting surface (length and width);
- the number of vibrations of the sorting surface per minute;
- the machine's mass;
- the personnel for service [1].

These characteristics are very important and should be studied very attentive for each sorting system, only by doing so, you can ensure a good functioning and the carrying out of the goal of the process in cause that is a very good separation (author).

3. Discussions

The sorting machines with rolls have the highest precision at sorting, but they frequently clog, especially when potatoes have a high degree of humidity or they have attached soil on them [2].

The sorting machines with the active organ type transporter belts have a small degree of harmfulness for potatoes, do not clog, but have a small coefficient of precision [3].

A high precision offers the machines with sieves or the machines with rolls (as mentioned above) [3].

The reduction of bruising and harm for potatoes can be done by covering the elements and active organs for sorting with a special type of rubber.

A deciding influence upon the sorting precision has the potatoes capacity of passing through the sieves. This capacity is influenced by: the frequency of the oscillations per minute of the sieves, by the amplitude of the oscillations and by the angle of tilting: as small as the value of these parameters is, as better the precision of sorting is [2].

For optimal values of these parameters, the productivity is reduced [2].

Upon the sorting precision, at the machines with sieves, the length of the sieves has an important influence, as larger the values of this parameter are, the precision is increased, but also the degree of bruising and harmfulness increases in the case of potato tubers [2].

The machines with rolling sieves are very simple to operate, but they are usually of small productivity [2].

The machines with rolling sieves separate mainly the tubers from the large fraction of consumption. The elimination of impurities and especially the particles of soil, before the potatoes will arrive on the sorting table, is done with other special organs as the transporter with wands, the oscillator grate, the vibratory bottom or the loading hopper [2].

The productivity and the precision of sorting are parameters that depend also by the distribution of the potatoes in fractions [2].

At the great majority of the sorting machines, the separation in fractions is done at the beginning by enrolling the whole mass of potatoes on the active organ or on the sector with small orifices, on which there are separated the small tubers. After that, the medium size tubers are separated by the larger ones [2].

Still, this sequence of operations is not totally accepted, because the sector with small orifices is charged with the whole mass of potatoes, from which it is being separated only a very small part of 10 % of small tubers. The rest of 40 % and 50 % are medium tubers and large tubers and this part displaces on the sorting surface, where it is being exposed to a high degree of harm and bruising [2].

By inverting the sequence of operations of separating the above mentioned fractions, the precision of sorting, the machine's productivity and the constructive aspect are done in better conditions [2].

4. Conclusions

Potato sorting is an operation that is done mainly by mechanical methods. The main disadvantage of mechanical sorting is the appearance of the bruising phenomenon at potatoes.

On the basis of knowing the constructive and functional characteristics of the potato sorting machines, there can be done some proposals for the optimization of some elements or points of interest. The functioning principles of simple potato sorting machines are useful in a better understanding of the sorting process and also in the understanding of the means of construction and functioning for the most complex machines.

It is important to realize a comparative evaluation of the advantages and disadvantages of potato sorting machines, with the role of identifying the elements that could be optimized.

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STUDY REGARDING THE CRUSHING RESISTANCE OF OLEAGINOUS SUNFLOWER SEEDS

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Abstract: *The extraction of vegetable oils from sunflower oilseeds (*Helianthus annuus L.*), can be achieved by various methods: mechanical pressing, using solvents (thinners) and supercritical fluids, GAME method, by combining various forms of the above mentioned methods. Whatever method is applied, in order to obtain more satisfactory results, before the actual extraction always reduce the grain size by milling them under the action of external forces. Given that sunflower seed downsizing is done in most cases by crushing (compression), a better understanding of the behavior of oilseeds subjected to this stress is necessary, and of the main influencing factors involved in the process development, as well. In this respect, this paper aimed at determining the maximum compressive strength of the following classes of oil: unshelled sunflower seeds, sunflower seeds partially shelled and sunflower oilseed kernel. Experiments have been made using the universal testing of materials Zwick - Roell Z005 equipment, the results were presented in the tables and their analysis was performed through three diagrams.*

Keywords: *crushing, strength, sunflower seeds, extraction, vegetable oil.*

1. Introduction

Worldwide, especially in industrialized countries, there is increasing trend in human consumption of vegetable oils, which can be explained by the advantages they pose in terms of food, compared with animal fats [3]: are more easily assimilated (predominantly unsaturated fatty acids as to the saturated ones); are nutritionally superior due to the presence of polyunsaturated fatty acids; contain less cholesterol for the human body; are more suitable for food products (mayonnaise, sauces, dressings etc.). In nature, all plant tissues contain vegetable fats in certain amounts (0.01 ... 70%), which would theoretically mean that there is a variety of vegetal sources from which oils for human consumption can be extracted [15]. Practically speaking, things are very different because in industry oils are extracted only from the parts of the plant that contain vegetal fats in economically acceptable quantities (at least 15 ... 20% of the vegetable fats, commonly found in seeds, fruits, kernels or germs).

As regards the extraction methods used, although many experiments are done to develop the procedures for the extraction of vegetable oils using supercritical fluids, and also by the GAME (Gas Assisted Mechanical Expression) method, currently, worldwide, we can talk about the existence of two dedicated extraction processes: mechanical pressing and solvent based

extraction, processes which may be applied independently or in succession, depending on the type of the raw oil, the oil content thereof and the degree of extraction required to be attained [7, 8, 18]. For example, in Romania, to extract vegetable oils from oleiferous seeds, in most cases the combined process is used: pressing the seed material, ensuring oil separation of up to 80...85% , is followed by the solvent based extraction, a method by which the oil is separated from the remainder (up to 99...99,5%) [18].

Regardless of the oilseed raw material or the extraction process chosen, on an industrial scale, before the actual extraction of the oil, the size of oleiferous seeds and fruits is reduced by grinding them under the action of external forces. Because it determines achievement of high yields in oil and positively influence future operations (hydrothermal conditioning, extraction and refining), grinding is considered as an essential operation in the preparation of the oil materials used to obtain vegetable oil [2, 8]. The analysis of the grinding operation showed that the occurrence of this phenomenon relies on the following mechanical methods: shearing, crushing, friction and impact. Although in most cases reducing the size of oleiferous seeds is done by the combination of different forms of the aforementioned methods mentioned, special attention is paid to the grinding process by

crushing. Originally designed as a specific process to high consistency oilseeds, grinding by crushing has become increasingly used over time, due to the simplicity and satisfactory results obtained. Although it is a very well known and pervasive method in the vegetable oils industry, few authors were concerned about studying the phenomenon in detail (Gupta and Das, 1997; Gupta and Das, 2000; Santalla and Mascheroni, 2003; Baumler et al., 2005; Ixtaina et al., 2008; Osoianu, 2010), reason for which the literature shows little evidence regarding this way of downsizing oleiferous products.

Given the above aspects and considering the importance of sunflower seeds for the Romanian oleiferous products industry, this study aimed at determining the resistance to grinding by crushing of the following classes of materials: unshelled sunflower seeds, sunflower seeds partially shelled and sunflower oilseed kernel.

2. Materials and methods

The oiliferous material which was the subject of experimental research (sunflower black seeds), was purchased from Brasov (45°38' N and 25°35' E), Romania. After removing the impurities in the weight of the seed, in order to ensure their physical purity, the cleaned oil material was maintained for two weeks at a temperature of 18° C, to achieve physiological maturity.

To determine the moisture of the physiological mature seeds, an electronic moisture meter, of Granomat type was used with the following technical characteristics: voltage – 110/230 V, 50/60 Hz; sizes – approx. 420 x 360 x 390 mm; weight – approx. 18 kg. Except for moisture, this device allows to determine other quality parameters such as: capacitance (dielectric constant), weight, hectoliter weight and sample temperature. In the case of the samples studied, the relative humidity indicated was 6 %, at a temperature of 18,3°C.

By manual unshelling of about two thirds of the samples whose moisture content was predetermined, two classes of oil materials were obtained: sunflower kernels (the total decortication) and sunflower seeds partially shelled (by partial decortication), which together with the remaining shelled seeds were the subject of further experimental research.

Husking oilseeds was necessary to cover the entire spectrum of oil products that can be grinded by crushing. Thus, in the case of sunflower oilseeds, according to the extraction

technology employed, the following classes of materials may be subjected to the grinding operation: totally de-husked sunflower seeds or oilseed kernels, partially un-peeled seeds and rough seeds.

Randomly, from the three categories listed above ten oilseeds were selected. For each seed individually the three main sizes were determined: length, width and thickness. The determination of these parameters was made using an electronic caliper Erba, based on digital technology, with a measuring range of between 0 and 150 mm. Also, using an analytical balance of Kern type (at least 0.2 grams up to 420 grams), was determined the weight of each oilseed.

The experimental research continued with determining resistance to grinding by crushing, for each oilseed in part, so it took thirty attempts to cover the entire range of materials available. The measurements were made using a universal material testing equipment (Z005), manufactured by the German company Zwick-Roell.

The Zwick-Roell Z005 equipment (fig. 1) can be used to determine the resistance to crushing, bending and shearing of the different kinds of materials. In order to conduct the tests, the equipment must be connected to a computer, the communication with the PC being achieved through a specialized software called Test Expert. The mentioned software stores in the Windows operating system all data resulting from the experiments made, enabling further processing. For a complex analysis of the data entered in the said software, these can be exported in Microsoft Excel. Measurements can be defined by means of two windows (fig. 2), namely: one window to impose working parameters and one for defining how to visualize the results obtained (graphs, charts, tables).

To achieve measurements, the testing equipment must be equipped with various instruments of special construction chosen depending on the category of application various materials are subjected to. In the case of sunflower seeds grinding by crushing, as special devices have been used two stainless steel plates, the tested seeds being placed between these plates, as it can be seen in fig. 1. The upper grinding plate is movable, and by its vertical movement, the oil seeds are trapped between the two plates, causing them to crush.

The Zwick-Roell Z005 equipment is equipped with two transducers (force gauge transducer and incremental position transducer) so that the crushing force according to the position of the

upper plate when entering in contact with the seed oil and until destruction of the seed integrity can be measured.

Fig. 1. Universal equipment Zwick-Roell Z005 to test the materials.

Fig. 2. Windows for defining how to visualize results and to impose working parameters.

3. Results and discussions

The actual determination of crushing strength started with the study of unshelled sunflower seeds. Oilseed characteristics of this group are shown in table 1, while fig. 3 shows graphically the variation of the strength during their individual crushing.

The data presented show that the maximum force of resistance to crushing of unshelled

sunflower seed, varies considerably, with values ranging 55...125 N. The factors that led to obtaining such results refer to the native structure, the physical condition, the geometrical shape and the size of the seeds which have been subjected to the experimental research.

Regarding the native structure and the physical condition, it can be stated unequivocally

that these parameters decisively influence the resistance to crushing. The position of oilseeds per head (inflorescence), which is especially important in the formation and development of the oleiferous material, the presence of cracks,

defects or discontinuities in the structure, are elements to be taken into account when determining the sunflower seeds resistance to crushing.

Table 1. *Features of unshelled sunflower seeds.*

Unshelled sunflower seeds	Weight [g]	Length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Maximum strength to crushing [N]
Test 1	0,084	13,26	6,78	4,25	112,94
Test 2	0,101	12,21	7,41	4,16	93,80
Test 3	0,147	15,27	7,22	4,84	118,98
Test 4	0,130	14,60	7,64	4,70	124,02
Test 5	0,135	12,35	8,18	5,93	102,62
Test 6	0,098	11,97	6,80	4,53	109,14
Test 7	0,061	10,97	5,48	3,33	55,02
Test 8	0,073	11,08	5,55	4,04	79,56
Test 9	0,092	11,52	6,63	4,34	105,42
Test 10	0,073	9,59	6,01	4,60	86,96

Fig. 3. *Variation in the strength at individual crushing of unshelled sunflower seeds.*

Regarding the seeds size, it must be said that the bigger size materials due to its structural heterogeneity, are battered at lower stress state and smaller specific deformations. Smaller sized materials have less cracks, defects or discontinuities in the mass, which makes the crushing effort much higher. In relation to the geometric shape, seeds which form is as close as possible to the ball shape are more resistant to grinding by crushing than oblong seeds.

From the moment the upper crushing plate machine of Zwick - Roell Z005 equipment, comes into contact with the oil seed and until crushing in the unshelled oily material a series of

events occur. Thus, firstly the shells deformation is made, followed by the emergence of the first cracks in the shell. Follows the rupture (partial) of the links between the core and the shell, the elastic and then the plastic deformation of the core and the emergence of the first cracks in the core (the first break point). When appears the first break point, the stress state created is maximum.

The stages of grinding by crushing, in the case of unshelled oilseeds (oily sunflower core) are presented graphically in fig. 4. The first stage (OA portion of the curve), starts when the upper crushing plate comes into contact with the upper

dehusked seed, this stage is characterized by the elastic deformation of micro-asperities in the oily core. As can be seen, in the first stage, the slope is reduced. In stage II, (the portion AB of the curve), there is an elastic deformation of the core. Stage III, (BC portion of the curve) is characterized by the elastic-plastic deformation of the core. Seed cracking occurs at point C, which is characterized by the maximum

resistance of the oleaginous seeds. Stage IV, (CD portion of the curve) characterizes seed grinding into smaller particles. In the first stage, the seed resistance decreases rapidly, which is corroborated with widening the existing cracks and occurrence of new ones. The local maximum curve appeared from cracking the newly obtained particles.

Fig. 4. Stages of grinding by crushing in the case of shelled sunflower seeds.

The features of the oily shelled seeds, which have been the object of experimental investigations are shown in the table 2 (features of shelled sunflower seeds), while fig. 5 shows graphically the variation of the strength during their individual crushing.

In this case also, the maximum resistance force to crushing varies within wide limits with values within the range of 15...86 N. The absence of the shell, which is considered the

mechanical system of the core defence, led to obtaining resistance forces approximately 50 N lower than for crushing unshelled oilseeds. Homogeneous values of the maximum resistance to crushing were obtained for partially unshelled sunflower seeds. The oilseed characteristics of this group are shown in table 3, while fig. 6 graphically shows the variation in the resistance force to individual crushing of partially unshelled sunflower seeds.

Table 2. Features of shelled sunflower seeds .

Sunflower oilseed core	Weight [g]	Length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Maximum strength to crushing [N]
Test 1	0,086	9,08	5,30	3,52	51,27
Test 2	0,096	10,12	5,32	3,29	67,00
Test 3	0,094	10,55	5,19	3,16	70,12
Test 4	0,087	11,64	4,96	2,88	31,88
Test 5	0,065	9,70	4,96	3,01	17,30
Test 6	0,095	11,50	5,09	2,79	85,89
Test 7	0,075	10,80	4,23	3,03	63,95
Test 8	0,065	7,79	5,10	3,72	27,48
Test 9	0,111	10,90	5,32	3,65	56,72
Test 10	0,047	9,24	3,81	2,92	15,34

Fig. 5. Variation in the strength at individual crushing of shelled sunflower seeds.

Table 3. Features of partially shelled sunflower seeds .

Partially shelled sunflower seeds	Weight [g]	Length [mm]	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Maximum strength to crushing [N]
Test 1	0,080	10,19	6,92	4,12	71,95
Test 2	0,083	11,77	6,14	3,66	63,31
Test 3	0,098	11,72	5,79	3,79	62,61
Test 4	0,117	13,28	7,42	4,19	84,39
Test 5	0,077	11,33	6,57	3,65	56,31
Test 6	0,079	11,23	6,65	3,16	51,89
Test 7	0,074	10,79	6,77	4,07	54,31
Test 8	0,071	11,15	6,71	3,26	46,70
Test 9	0,072	10,19	6,17	4,31	44,70
Test 10	0,098	11,13	7,52	4,42	88,11

Fig. 6. Variation in the strength at individual crushing of partially shelled sunflower seeds.

4. Conclusions

Grinding oilseeds involves reducing their size, as a result of the action the external forces. Because it determines achievement of high yields in oil and positively influence future operations grinding is considered as an essential operation in the preparation of the oil materials used to obtain the vegetable oil.

Special care is paid to the grinding by crushing procedure, which is increasingly used in oil product industry, due to the simplicity and satisfactory results obtained.

To be able to develop suitable grinding equipment and for the sake of optimizing power consumption in obtaining the oil, solid

knowledge of how raw materials are downsized is required.

In the case of sunflower seeds, according to the extraction technology applied, the following classes of materials may be subjected to the grinding operation: totally de-husked sunflower seeds or oilseed kernels, partially un-peeled seeds and rough seeds.

Given the various factors of influence, the behavior and the characteristics of the three different classes of oil materials, it was established that the maximum force of resistance to crushing may vary within very wide limits even within the same category of oil material.

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KAZAKHSTAN AT THE TURN OF THE 21ST CENTURY

GULZIRA SYDYKBAYEVA

Abstract: *The paper presents an overview on the economical situation of Kazakhstan since achieving its independence in 1991. New challenges occur in this period and various methods for reforming and macroeconomic development. The rapid economic growth in the 21st century was to a high extent based on the revenues from natural resources. Shortly after independence fields of gas and oil were discovered in Kazakhstan. Interest was huge among foreign oil companies. The economy became oriented around export on oil and gas, which had strongly positive economical effects. Some reforms call for more reforms, they are interdependent and hence self-reinforcing and Kazakhstan's economic transition has been the smoothest among the Central Asian states.*

Keywords: *socialist economy, market economy, transition process, centralized banking system.*

1. Introduction

The breakdown of the Soviet empire initiated the largest transition from a socialist economy to a market economy. Since independence in 1991 Kazakhstan has been undertaking comprehensive reforms aimed at dismantling the command economy and creating a market economy. The economic transition of Kazakhstan coincided with independence and the set-up of new institutions and legal framework. Hence, the transition process did not only change institutions but in some cases a creation of these. Kazakhstan was the last state to declare its independence from the USSR and stayed close to Russia during the initial phase of independence in many respects.

2. Economical reform in Kazakhstan

Kazakhstan followed the Russian transition process. The goal was to create a well functioning market economy through a range of measures aiming at liberalizing, stabilizing and privatizing the economy. Kazakhstan inherited an economic system and many other aspects from the Soviet Union with major problems. The capital stock was old-fashioned as a result of decades of low investment; production was concentrated to industries and agriculture while the service sector was underdeveloped. Poor infrastructure generated inefficient production. In all, the centralization and heavy bureaucracy were prime obstacles to an effective economic environment. Kazakhstan and the rest of the former Soviet Union further suffered from huge ecological problems, e.g. the catastrophic drying

up of the Aral Sea, nuclear pollution in the military testing zones, and pollution and bad water in industrial areas.

The transition has been a success in terms of privatization and macroeconomic development and the radical consequent path had positive economic effects. The part of the privatization in 1995-1996 included a range of large enterprises. Vouchers were used. It is comparable to the privatization in Russia. Most of the post communist countries used voucher privatization to some extent in their reform program. The method is based on vouchers that are distributed among the citizens who can trade them for shares at auction. It is relatively easy and fast to launch, the equal distribution of the vouchers benefits the entire population, and it solves the problem of lack of domestic demand for property.

A market economy requires an effective financial sector. Private banks created through privatization of state owned banks, as well as encouraging the emergence of new banks and establishment of foreign banks, are necessary for investments and important for the privatization process in general. During 1990's the centralized banking system was slowly changed, and smaller banks could take over some functions, although still being dependent on the USSR State Bank. In 1991, no really independent banking and financial institutions existed in Kazakhstan.

The Kazakh State Bank was renamed National Bank of Kazakhstan after independence and restrictions on private independent banking and financial institutions were lifted. New commercial banks were created, both private and state owned. Also foreign banks were

establishing on the Kazakh financial market such as Citibank, HSBC and UniCredit

Reformation of the exchange rate policy was hence of major importance in order to facilitate internal and external trade. At independence a significant amount of domestic trade became foreign trade with Russia, a country that Kazakhstan's economy was, and still is, tightly integrated with. Newly independent countries might introduce an independent currency, as in the case of Kazakhstan. The exchange rate is supposed to be unified, but in some cases it may be partly controlled initially in order to avoid negative effects of speculative flows. One of the major steps for the socialist economies was to change the trade that mainly was pursued with other socialist countries and to enter the world trading system. The reform process must primarily break down the state monopoly on trade in order to let enterprises trade freely. The process promotes price liberalization and improves the allocation of resources. The shortages of consumer products in these countries implied strong public support for liberalizing trade.

Since the means of production and the companies were owned by the state in the socialist economies it was necessary to privatize a significant part of the state-owned enterprises (SOEs) and reform all of them. Key aspect of the transition process, privatization of SOEs and state properties such as real estate and infrastructure is one of the most difficult tasks of economic transition, economically, politically, juridical, and practically. It is a very complex process to divide the ownership in a country where everything was owned by the state, and the tradition of private ownership was limited.

The independent state of Kazakhstan started with a significant budget deficit. An abolishment of consumer price subsidies was effected as part of the price reform. Taxes used to be paid by a small number of state enterprises and collected through the state bank system. Kazakhstan had established an own system with a new tax agency, which was rather complicated. Different agencies competed with each other and there was initially no monopoly on taxation. In 1992 the old tax system was replaced by a new tax system based on VAT, an enterprise profits tax and a personal income tax. In 1995 a new tax code was enacted, based on international standards. The pension system was completely reorganized with the outcome that citizens could choose whether to invest in private or state funds

Kazakhstan possessed huge natural resources and the main fields of oil and gas were not explored before independence. Furthermore, Kazakhstan also possessed vast fertile agricultural land, as well as forests and minerals. The country has approximately one third of the world's deposits of chromium and manganese and significant reserves of tungsten, lead, zinc, copper, bauxite and phosphorus, as well as reserves of coal and iron.

The *Commonwealth of Independent States* (CIS) was established as the Soviet Union collapsed in December 1991. The main feature of this loose organization was the common currency, the ruble. Payments for inter-Soviet republics' trade were settled through the balances of the national banks of the republics and the central bank of the Soviet Union. The central bank of Kazakhstan and other republics banks retained the right to issue non-cash credits in rubles. The implication was that the states could diminish their fiscal deficit by issuing ruble credits while mainly other states within the ruble zone had to take the inflation effect. However, became impossible to coordinate the new central banks and maintain monetary discipline. The countries left the ruble zone one by one and the Russian central bank started to change the banknotes in Russian territory. In November 1993 Kazakhstan introduced the tenge as the ruble zone collapsed. Thereby Kazakhstan could pursue an independent monetary and exchange rate policy. Hyperinflation however continued, and the tenge had to float freely. The central bank began to target a stable exchange rate as well as low inflation.

The rapid economic growth in the 21st century was to a high extent based on the revenues from natural resources. Shortly after independence immense fields of gas and oil were discovered in Kazakhstan. Interest was huge among foreign oil companies. The economy became oriented around export on oil and gas, which had strongly positive effects on the growth

After the economic turning point in 1995 Kazakhstan experienced difficult time in 1998 as a result of the Russian financial crisis. The crises can be seen as exogenous, but the grave effects on the Kazakh economy unmasked the vulnerability of the economy. Once again, Kazakhstan followed measures taken by Russia, including a major devaluation of the currency to stimulate the economy

The macro-economic reforms in Kazakhstan have been relatively successful, helped by vast

reserves of natural resources. The price reform initiated in 1992 was radical and comprehensive and liberalized prices by removing price controls and reducing subsidies. Kazakhstan followed the reforms of Russia in several senses. One major difference between the countries however is the result of the privatization.

The tax system as well as banking and investment laws quickly followed international standards and promoted investment. The privatization was relatively successful, although to some extent characterized by lack of transparency. Trade and foreign investment have been encouraged through elimination of trade monopoly, simplified regulations and have been successful.

The economic situation in the mid-1990s was difficult and the reform program slowed down. Due to the financial crisis in Russia and decreased oil-prices, the economy of Kazakhstan again turned downward in 1998. However, the increases of world oil prices in 1999 combined with devaluation of the tenge pulled the economy out of recession, and since 2000 Kazakhstan has experienced an impressive growth.

The agriculture that used to be important has not been the subject of major investments which has resulted in inadequate infrastructure such as roads, processing equipment and farm inputs. The banks have not provided much-needed credits for farm expansion. The oil boom of the 2000s gave Kazakhstan the possibility of continuing with reforms and finance program to ameliorate the social sector.

The economic dependence on natural resources is structured in a way that distribution of income and wealth is not likely to change in the future unless more radical reforms are pursued. The financial centers of Astana and Almaty will continue to benefit from the growth whereas the rural areas will continue to be left behind. Furthermore, the deep recession in Kazakhstan

was accompanied by a sharp increase in mortality, migration and population crisis, and a steep rise in unemployment.

Conclusions

Nonetheless, the economic reforms in Kazakhstan indicate considerable progress towards establishing a well working market economy. The country has achieved a sound macroeconomic environment. The rapid and comprehensive reform program was followed by a steep decline in output, but the implementation of structural measures had positive economic effects after a few years.

Some reforms call for more reforms, they are interdependent and hence self-reinforcing and Kazakhstan's economic transition has been the smoothest among the Central Asian states. This can be explained by relatively good initial conditions, an ambitious transition program with rapid and comprehensive reforms, and vast natural resources.

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INFLUENCE OF HEAT TREATMENT AND PRE-PACKAGING ON QUALITY OF BALANCED PRODUCTS

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Abstract: *This article presents the results of studies of physical and chemical properties and microbiological safety of rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts subjected to gentle heat processing with pre-packaging in polymeric materials. Found that the products are of high biological value, maintain physical, chemical and microbiological parameters ological without special cooling for 6 - 8 hours.*

Keywords: *plastic film, vacuum packaging, delicate cycle heat treatment, amino-acid score, biological value, microbiological safety.*

1. Introduction

When cooking using various combinations of vegetable and animal raw materials to ensure a balanced composition of the finished product on the fats, proteins, carbohydrates, macro- and micronutrients. The combination of aquatic organisms in the product (fish or squid), rice, onions and carrots can provide balanced product's composition on key nutrients and high organoleptic properties. The traditional methods and temperatures of heat treatment (more than 373 K) in the animal feed are processes denature protein components, accompanied by weight loss by 30 - 35% and the change in amino acid composition in cereals is the cooking and degradation of polysaccharides, accompanied by binding of significant amounts of moisture, processing carrots and onions by destructive processes is released moisture and weight by 20 - 25% and 15 - 20%, respectively. Lowering the temperature of the treatment and pre-packaging of semi-finished product before cooking allows one to preserve the food and biological value of raw materials, increase yield and shelf life of the finished product [1, 4].

The aim is to study the physical and chemical properties and microbiological safety indicators rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts in storage, with low-temperature heat treatment schedule and pre-packaging of prescription ingredients in dishes polymer bags.

2. Main part

The object of study - a mixture of onion (particle size $0,5 \times 0,5$ cm), carrots (particle size $1,5 \times 0,2 \times 0,2$ cm) long grain rice polished Grade 1, as well as squid and fish (carp) (pieces weighing 15 g) packed in a polymeric heat-resistant film, subjected Convection treatment at different temperatures.

To reduce the length of cooking rice subjected to preliminary hydration at 353 K for 30 min, the mixture made up as follows: rice hydrated - 110 g, chopped onions - 20 g, sliced carrots - 20 g fillet of carp - 50 g or sliced bird squid - 55 g, 15 g of extra moisture to recipes with squid, the total weight of the product batch - 200 This ratio will provide the best conditions for the transition moisture, initially associated with animal protein and localized in plant cells of onions and carrots in the related polysaccharides rice state [2, 3]. From the perspective of redistribution bound moisture in the system optimal relations between the components are for rice-vegetable mixture with squid: rice hydrated - 55,0%, chopped onion - 10,0%, sliced squid - 27,0%, water - 8,0% for rice-vegetable mixture with carp: rice hydrated - 60%, sliced carrots - 6%, chopped onions - 9%, carp fillet - 25% [3].

These components are packed in plastic bags with a vacuum-pack the unit and subjected to heat treatment in the temperature range $T=363 - 368$ K, humidity coolant 100% for $\tau=9-11$ min.

In the study of combined products were determined mass fraction of protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals, amino acid composition, amino acid difference coefficient, biological value, acid and peroxide value. To determine the benefits of the de-

veloped method of cooking as a control sample studied mixture of the same composition, cooked with steam without prior packaging at 368 K. The experimental data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Performance of biological value of rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts

Item name	Rice-vegetable mixture with squid		Rice-vegetable mixture with carp	
	Sample treated in the traditional way	Packed sample treated in the combi steamer	Sample treated in the traditional way	Packed sample treated in the combi steamer
Physical and chemical properties				
Protein content, %	19,02	23,06	27,06	30,27
Fat content, %	0,68	0,58	18,34	21,53
Mass fraction of carbohydrates, %	52,13	60,44	52,32	60,44
Acid number, mg KOH / g	-	-	1,94	1,02
Peroxide value,% J2	-	-	0,03	0,03
Zinc, mg / kg	8,7	9,3	9,2	10,1
Copper, mg / kg	1,9	2,1	2,2	2,3
Manganese, mg / kg	0,25	0,28	0,31	0,33
Vitamin A, mg / kg	1,1	1,7	4,2	6,8
Vitamin B1, mg / kg	0,17	0,31	0,19	0,38
Vitamin B2 mg / kg	0,95	1,55	0,90	1,58
Vitamin C, mg / kg	6,10	10,5	6,0	11,0
Vitamin D3, mg / kg	1,25	2,2	1,10	2,6
Vitamin PP, mg / kg	723,5	944,1	714,7	945,2
The amino acid composition				
Isoleucine	5,40	4,62	4,35	5,97
Leucine	12,37	14,0	13,71	13,72
Lysine	12,02	12,69	15,05	13,67
Methionine + cystine	4,69	5,19	5,50	8,4
Phenylalanine + tyrosine	9,05	9,41	11,95	11,97
Threonine	5,85	5,7	7,34	7,12
Valine	5,87	5,24	6,86	7,74
Tryptophan	1,24	1,25	1,20	1,21
Indicators of biological value				
Ratio of amino acid differences soon,%	17,30	18,20	22,50	23,60
Biological value,%	75,10	81,80	71,10	76,20
Coefficient of utility (U),%	0,77	0,78	0,72	0,73
Figure comparable redundancy of essential amino acids (σ_c), %	10,14	9,83	12,45	12,02
Utilization rate of protein, %	78,50	78,0	73,45	73,0

Analyzing the data in Table 1, it can be noted that the numerical values of indices reach their maximum values in the samples packaged rice-vegetable mixes, processed at low temperature heat treatment. Thus, these mixtures have a high content of vitamins (25%), minerals (15%), protein, and fat (10%). Maximal changes concentration of essential amino acids accounted for isoleucine (20%), leucine (22%), methionine and cystine (12%), valine (15%), and limiting amino acids are in the samples with squid - tryptophan, isoleucine, methionine + cystine, in samples with carp - tryptophan, isoleucine, threonine. In addition, minor changes qualitative ratio of amino acids in a protein in all the samples irrespective of the method of heat cooking.

From Table 1, it also follows that pre-packaging rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts in polymer bags,

followed by low-temperature heat treatment has a positive effect on the performance of the biological value of intermediate inputs. Compared to samples treated with the traditional method, the biological value of the samples packed rice-vegetable mixture is incremented by 7-10%.

Studies in rice-vegetable mixture with hydrobionts The changes organoleptic microbiological safety during storage at temperatures: $276 \pm 0,1$ K and $298 \pm 0,1$ K.

When sensory evaluation of samples of the following factors: taste and odor – 60 points, structure and consistency – 30 points, color and appearance - 10 points. The results of sensory evaluation rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts in the diagram (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Dynamics of changes in organoleptic rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts during storage at different ways of cooking:

a – machining in the traditional way, and b – low temperature heat treatment with vacuum pre-packaging

In the samples rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts during storage, study of aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms, Escherihia coli, Staphylo-

coccus aureus, Clostridium perfringens and Listeria monocytogenes. Results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 - Changes in the microbiological safety of rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts in storage

Item name	Rice-vegetable mixture with squid					Rice-vegetable mixture with carp				
	Sample treated in the traditional way		Packed sample treated in the combi steamer			Sample treated in the traditional way		Packed sample treated in the combi steamer		
	Storage time, day (with T= $298 \pm 0,1$ K)									
	1	2	1	5	7	1	2	1	5	7
Colony-forming unit, CFU/g	$4,5 \times 10^3$	$2,1 \times 10^5$	less than 1,0	$2,4 \times 10^2$	$4,5 \times 10^4$	$3,2 \times 10^3$	$4,4 \times 10^5$	less than 1,0	$4,1 \times 10^2$	$3,6 \times 10^4$

	$\times 10^1$					$\times 10^1$				
	Storage time, day (with $T=276\pm 0,1$ K)									
	1	2	5	10	15	1	2	5	10	15
	7,7 $\times 10^1$	8,9 $\times 10^3$	2,2 $\times 10^1$	1,6 $\times 10^3$	4,2 $\times 10^4$	5,4 $\times 10^1$	7,5 $\times 10^3$	3,4 $\times 10^1$	2,7 $\times 10^3$	4,7 $\times 10^4$

Analyzing the data in Table 2, we can conclude that for the experimental rice-vegetable mixtures hydrobionts time to reach critical values of aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms, hazardous to the health of the consumer (5×10^4 colony-forming unit (CFU/g) depends on the temperature conditions of storage. So much for the samples, the storage temperature which was $T=298\pm 0,1$ K, time to reach the critical values of aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms in two times less than for the samples with temperature storage $T=276\pm 0,1$ K, i.e. 7 and 15 days, respectively.

In the control samples during the critical value aerobic and facultative anaerobic microorganisms, was 24 and 48 hours at a temperature storage $T=298\pm 0,1$ и $T=276\pm 0,1$ K respectively.

During the study period of storage in the experimental samples were not detected: *Escherihia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Clostridium perfringens* and *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Conclusions

Analyzing the experimental data, we can conclude that the use of low-temperature heat cooking food with a preliminary vacuum packing, allowing processed foods increase the performance of the biological value

of 10-15%, in addition to save 20-25% of the vitamins, 10-15% minerals, as well as to ensure the preservation of safety at the required level without special cooling product 6 - 7 days, with the result that the product can be recommended for special nutrition (tourism, expeditions, emergency situations, etc.).

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RESEARCH ON THE RELATIVE POSITIONS OF CABLE CAR DURING EXTERNAL MECHANICAL DISTURBANCES

E. HODIRNAU, M. HODIRNAU

Abstract: This paper presents a brief history of public transport cable, wind types and her influences of the cable car transport, their component parts and measures of oscillation made by the wind and crossing pillars. These vertical movements can cause a cable to oscillate vertically in a similar way in a thunderstorm currents. The movements induced a smaller scale gusts can cause strong reactions from a cable car. At the same time, the movements induced a smaller scale gusts can cause strong reactions from a cable car.

Keywords: funicular, cable, cable transport, wind influence, wind types, pillar.

1. Introduction

The transport of men and goods by means of cabledrawn transport systems was known even in ancient times. Early Chinese historical drawings demonstrate that this principle was already in use very early for material transport. The ropes used were made of plant fibres, e.g. bamboo fibres. In the Middle Ages a monocable aerial ropeway was depicted in a book by Johannes Hartlieb (Fig. 1).

During the course of the Industrial Revolution, the invention of the steel cable by the German mining official Albert in 1834 heralded a period of lively development of the various cable-drawn transport systems [7].

While initially development mainly focused on funicular railways such as the Cable Car Line in San Francisco, 1872 (see Figure 2), later interest

turned to aerial ropeways, which only came into operation for passenger transport shortly after 1900. A fine example is the reversible aerial ropeway in San Sebastian, Spain opened 1907 (Figure 3). Various technical systems have evolved over the decades. For example, more recent systems can be classified according to the type of track (carrier) used. Figure 4 shows an overview of the various systems, which are naturally in use with very diverse frequency.

Bicable aerial ropeways and funiculars will subsequently be described in more detail. In addition, inclined lifts are intrinsically a modified form of funicular railway, but are subject to lift regulations and therefore cannot be directly regarded as funiculars [8]

Figure 1: Drawing of a monocable aerial ropeway from A.D. 1411

Figure 2: Cable Car, San Francisco, 1872

Figure 3: Reversible aerial ropeway in San Sebastian, Spain, 1907[8]

2. Wind types and it's influences of the cable car transport

Depending on wind strength during cable car route or the climb or the descent, cable car passes over the peaks and valleys over areas where atmospheric turbulence is formed and protected from the wind by shaded areas where there might be other types of turbulence.

Wind energy sources are given by atmospheric turbulence. Atmospheric turbulence are the result of movement at different speeds in different directions vertically or horizontally.

Atmospheric turbulence is based on four main sources:

- a convection.
- b friction surface.
- c orographic waves.
- d Energy flow in layers turbulent environments.

Except friction surface above mechanisms produce turbulence on a scale too large to shake a cable car. In general, the initial rupture generates turbulence of the cable car movement. The main categories of the cablecar turbulence can be described by reference to these energy sources.

Convective turbulence: this category includes all the turbulence of the cable car where vertical accelrații occur as a result of hydrostatic instability.

Turbulence thunderstorms: In general, vertical currents are intensifying progressing to the top within a Cumulus cloud asset to the upper third of the cloud. The activity is stronger at

intermediate levels than under a cloud around the base and near the tip.

At the same time, there are cases. A strong or violent turbulence may accompany heavy rains falling from beneath the cloud base parts, producing strong currents and turbulence descendants outside the cloud. From the upper and lower turbulence can often come within the area of activity or result from compensatory movements from outside the cloud.

Descending currents are very strong and are generally more significant at the bottom of the cloud Cumulonimbus. Descending air is forced to expand horizontally near the earth's surface, creating often violent phenomena

Vertical advection (currents ascending or descending) of the current turbulent energy in a thunderstorm turbulence tends to disperse. A strong turbulence can thus not be limited to a specific region in the cloud.

Large-scale vertical currents that accompany thunderstorms associated cold front lines can hardly be considered as sources of turbulence. It is worth their attention and interaction with the horizontal wind field.

Mechanical turbulence: often called friction, resulting from the interaction between land surface and the wind in the first 2000m in altitude. This type of turbulence energy is released in a broad spectrum, which depends primarily on the roughness of the terrain.

Turbulence energy of the cable car, in this case, comes directly from the flow medium and large-scale turbulent motions.

The cable car turbulence intensity depends on the following factors:

- a wind speed
- b Surface roughness
- c. Height above ground
- d. hydrostatic stability - thermal energy availability from the base.
- e. release of latent heat, if condensation.

Strong winds cause an apparent turbulence due to forced lifting of air from the surface. In the lower layers occurs as a mixture, which affects close to equilibrium regardless. Heat gain or loss through heating or cooling of the surface influence the mechanical turbulence as follows:

- Acting as a source or as a source of energy of turbulent motion.
- Causing thickening layer of mixture.

Orographic wave turbulence

Orographic turbulence has the following two sources of energy:

- a) ordinary mechanical turbulence that occurs near the peaks, and not limited to areas where we where well developed.
- b) gravitational waves partially or fully formed, providing additional energy is correlated with the strong turbulence categories.

Wave motion is often once regular double vertical amplitude reaches 2 km or more, and vertical velocity values of 5-10m / s are relatively frequent.

In which formats the mountains above average, while the maximum vertical currents are of the order of 25m / s, some isolated reports have shown speeds of the order of 40m / s It appears that there is often an asymmetry in the flow, rising and falling currents with different speeds.

Fig. 4. Wind Hazards

These vertical movements can cause a cable to oscillate vertically in a similar way in a thunderstorm currents. At the same time, the movements induced a smaller scale gusts can cause strong reactions from a cable car. For example, a cable car route that meets you moving with normal speed gusts of around 12m / s, are likely to have serious oscillation. Thus, in order to prevent of the cable car speed reduction is recommended in the presence of orographic waves, even when it seems regular flow may be encountered turbulence suddenly without any warning.

One can distinguish different types of flowing mountain will wind regime. In the case of very weak winds, Wave has a regular flow of small amplitude in the ridge, with small vertical currents and no other phenomenon downstream.

If the wind speed increases, the vortex can form

a semi-permanent, large, leeward side of the mountain, a regular wave of small amplitude above.

Detachable chairlifts are designed in a 2, 4, 6, or 8 ways with places for large transport capacities up to 4000 persons / hour. They are suitable both touristic seasons, providing optimal solutions for winter sports enthusiasts, passengers being forced to remove their skis during transport.

This system provides a solution for loading and unloading in the best conditions of safety, reducing speed to about 0.2 m / s, allowing the persons with disabilities or children to travel comfortably

All sensors were mounted in center of mass of a full loaded cabin for recording all forces

and movement filed by the passenger during travel.

Fig. 5: Arrangement of the sensors on the cabin

Applications using Sensor Insider Pro V 3.1.1, three-axis acceleration sensor BOSCH DMA222, MMC328X MEMS magnetic field sensor (Fig. 6), orientation sensor MEMS magnetic sensor orientation 3, data were recorded using a data acquisition board and processed using an electronic computer. As we can see altitude measured by GPS has a large error of 46 m due to

shading by shielding the GPS signal pillars. Another measurement error using the GPS position can occur on slopes with Northern exhibition because most satellites are in equatorial area for which the angle is seen moving object on the Northern slope almost coincides with the slope.

Fig. 6: Compared altitude between GPS sensor and barometric sensor

In Figure 7 you can see the following variations: X-axis a lateral oscillation of the cable car is registered, the graphics stand out three areas between minimum and maximum ± 3 degrees, highs occurring in the area near the poles and after passing them. Lateral oscillation frequency of the cabin value increases when approaching the pole because the pole time relative length of cable that consists pendulum is suspended cab goes down to 0 and the cabin remains only to oscillate around the axis arm reducing cable support is from a few tens of meters in length between the center of mass of the cabin-arm assembly - roller battery that is 4.2

m another important oscillation of the cable car is when it enters the station registering values between -6 and -3 degrees during track position as cabin she was not sitting horizontally tilted by 3 degrees due to car occupants distribution un uniform and because most people are more densely near the door. Another reason may be a tilted cab is that supporting point position of the cable car is ready eccentric fate of the center of symmetry of the cabin by 70 mm, which makes the cabin varying load angle that makes it the vertical axis during movement may vary by ± 3 degrees.

Fig. 7: Variation oscillations recorded by the magnetic field sensor

Conclusion

The functioning of the entire system is supervised not only by professional staff, but also by road safety assistance in that country, controlling and making periodical inspection of the system. Thus, funiculars are tested in different applications, when they move from upstream to downstream or vice versa maximum number of people carrying at the maximum weight.

The electronic system and handling of the elevator are designed to lead to a great safety, and also be resistant to errors that occurred during operation. Mechanical parts are characteristic of robust design and rigorous testing, this means that the piece that can withstand without damage, a request larger than that for which it was designed, and prototype parts are subjected to rigorous testing before manufacture in series.

For convenience and durability, it is necessary for the elevator to work with minimum resonance. Resonance comes from cable

movement on wheels and thereby induces vibrations in the pillars and twisted pair cable.

These vibrations are trying to be reduced by coating the rubber castors, this coating is important to prevent the cable slipping wheels, wheels string being suspended by springs. The resonance is diminished by the fact because gondola or cabin is set on the console with a thick rubber pad. However, resonance can be clearly heard and felt, especially when they pass over wheels pillar of support.

In this example, various sensors measuring altitude can be seen that mountain canyons GPS sensor can give large errors in turn pressure sensor has a much better accuracy.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE MODULE FOR DETERMINING THE TEMPERATURE FIELD IN THE HIGH PRESSURE CHAMBER

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Abstract: *The article considers developed on the basis of research design layout of the experimental setup for the study of the combined action of high pressure and ultrasound on food raw material and products. Revealed the appointment of separate modules and developed a system for automated control of the research process.*

Keywords: *high pressure, ultrasound, combined process, the temperature field.*

In recent years, the power structure of the Ukrainian population trace greater negative changes associated with the reduction in dietary essential nutrients - vitamins, proteins, etc. Never a food problem needed as much attention as in the past 10 years because it is available now; the desire of people to live a healthy life necessarily involves the right attitude to food. It is known that the food contains nutrients that provide energy and are necessary for growth and the maintenance of life fabric, which the human body cannot produce on their own and therefore must receive from outside. Therefore, one of the priorities of the food industry is to supply the population with high-quality, nutritionally adequate and safe foods. The main route of increasing the usefulness of domestic food use is in modern food technology solutions to minimize the negative impact on the nutrients applied as separate operations, and the whole process. This requires a search for new approaches, which should base basic research in the field of food chemistry, biotechnology, microbiology, food hygiene, which will reveal the nature of the processes that are responsible for changes in the quality of products during their production and subsequent storage. Currently, there are a variety of methods of processing of products in order to extend their storage: thermal pasteurization and sterilization, the use of chemicals and preservatives, ultrafiltration, electro processing methods (electromagnetic fields treatment of high and ultra-high frequency, radiation pasteurization, ultraviolet irradiation, elastic waves processing, the use of electric fields of low and high voltages, use of AC and DC magnetic fields). Each of these methods has certain limits of application, advantages and disadvantages. International association of research institutes and universities collaborating in the field of food safety (The Safe Consortium), which is working on the entire spectrum of issues related to safety and nutritional value of food,

have been discussed almost all the innovative technologies [1]. There were identified three major trends in research on new technologies. The first trend is associated with the effectiveness of technology in relation to the well-being products and microbiological study of mechanisms of inactivation. The second trend involves the use of combined techniques that can combine the best of the individual technologies, but their combination reduces inherent in each of these negative factors. The third trend describes the importance of commercialization of these technologies. In the development of any new technology is extremely important to make sure that the process is working properly and process goals have been achieved. Therefore, the introduction of any new technology requires careful study, which requires the development of teaching ensure the pilot. Successful combination of physical factors corresponds to one of the latest technology, which is growing rapidly in the developed world - the so-called MTS-technology (manothermosonication) - a technique that combines the processing of ultrasound, heat and pressure [2,3]. This technology combines best effects of individual factors, which allows obtaining products with a high content of nutrients at a significantly extended storage periods. This paper is devoted to development of the experimental setup for studying the combined effect of high pressure up to 200 MPa, ultrasound and temperature. Schematic diagram of the apparatus for carrying out research on the influence of processing MTS (UMTS) in the foods is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of UMST

In Figure 1, thin solid lines show the single channel pipelines working liquids, triple thin continuous lines - electrical connections of electromechanical and electronic devices UMST; dotted line circled cylinders of low and high pressure hydraulic booster (ГМ). Low pressure UMST channel consists of a gear oil pump (H) with a nominal pressure of 16 MPa, motor (ЭП) 2 kW, 10 micron filter (Ф), oil pan (M), pressure gauge to 16 MPa (M1), safety valve 16 MPa (ПДК), a hydraulic throttle (ГД), shut-off valve (ЗК). The channel consists of a high-pressure chamber and the pressure gauge to 200 MPa (M2). Sketch of the chamber pressure with ultrasonic transducers and the heater is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Sketch of the pressure chamber with ultrasonic transmitters and a heater, where И1 - top ultrasonic emitter РЖВД - working fluid pressure, И2 - lower ultrasonic emitter, НК - heater chamber

Gear oil pump (H) is used to convert mechanical energy of motor (ЭП) in the hydraulic power of the low-pressure fluid. As energy transmitter used belt drive. Magnitude of the pressure fluid РЖВД low pressure at the pump outlet is set by

speed of the male rotor connected to the rotor of the ЭП. Pump rated operation provides power parameters ЭП and belt drive gear ratio and supports hydraulic load on both channels. In nominal mode, the pump operates at rated load and the current pressure РЖВД (P) which is equal to rated output (P_{np}, np - «nominal pressure») $P = p_{np}$. In this way, a maximum duration of the life of the pump is achieved. The pressure hydraulic force РЖВД has a value that is sufficient to create the maximum working fluid pressure of high pressure (РЖВД) acting directly on the sample in a high-pressure chamber (K). From the output of the pump (H) РЖВД passes through a filter (F), which is designed to remove heterogeneous solid particles larger than 10 microns. In parallel with the filter (Ф) connected dial gauge (M1), the valve (ПДК), safety valve (ЗК) and the hydraulic throttle (ГД). Manometer (M1) is controlled by the pressure P. Depending on the total hydraulic resistance device low pressure channel P can varied from minimum (P_{min}) to maximal (P_{max}). P_{min} is a constant value which is determined by the lowest total hydraulic flow resistance РЖВД and P_{max} - is variable and depends on the flow resistance, which is regulated. When $P = P_{min}$ pump operates with minimal overhead, almost at idle, and when $P = P_{max}$ - pump loaded. Running the pump at maximum load corresponds to nominal operation, and the maximum pressure P_{max} output equal to P_{np}. РЖВД Pressure range from P_{min} to P_{max} is a working channel for low-pressure setting.

To achieve the required in the experiment values of maximum pressure РЖВД P_{max}, needed safety valve (ЗПК). Its principle of operation is based on balancing the compressive force of closing spring (F_{sf}, sf - «spring force») and the pressure force РЖВД (FP) at the current pressure P. When $FP = F_{sf}$, hydraulic force РЖВД acquires its maximum value $FP = F_{pmax}$ and current equal to the maximum pressure $P = P_{max}$. Relief valve setting at P_{max} shall regulate operated compression force of closing spring using the screw pair. When the current strength of the РЖВД pressure in the pipeline less than compression force closing spring, the valve is closed. As soon as the pressure РЖВД will be more than compression force of closing spring, the valve opens, and through part of the working fluid is discharged into the oil pan (M). As a result, the pressure РЖВД in the pipeline begins to fall, and when it again becomes less elastic force of the closing spring, the valve closes. The process of balancing the compressive force of closing spring

and pressure РЖНД forces is automatic. Shut-off valve (ЗК) can be in the two extreme states of its flow area - "open" or "closed" and is designed to fully open / shut-off fluid flowing under pressure in low-pressure cylinder (ЦНД) of the hydraulic booster (ГМ). Depending on the ЗК, there are two basic modes of UMTS operation: - at constant pressure, when the ЗК is in the "closed" - with alternating pressure when ЗК is in the "open" position. ЗК carries out the fixation of the current values of pressure РЖНД and РЖВД thus fixing the hydrostatic pressure acting on the sample. Hydraulic throttle (ГД) is a device with an adjustable value of its flow area which is designed to change the total pressure loss in the low РЖНД pressure channel flow. When the hydraulic throttle fully opened, its flow area takes its maximum value. In this case, РЖНД flow resistance determined by the smallest possible total of the resistance in the channel hydraulic devices and РЖНД pressure at the outlet of the pump equal to the minimum $P = P_{min}$. While the pump pumps РЖНД in the sump through hydraulic choke (pump operation with minimal overhead in idle mode). When the hydraulic throttle is fully closed - the РЖНД flow through the throttle stops. In this case, the pump operates at maximum load, creating at its output a given maximum pressure installed by pressure relief valve. Gauge M2 is used to monitor the hydrostatic pressure acting on the sample. This pressure is created by the working fluid (ПЕС-3) channels of high pressure. According to our calculations РЖНД maximum pressure is $P_{max} = P_{np} = 16$ МПа, the maximum РЖВД pressure (maximum pressure) is 200 МПа. In this case, the multiplication coefficient $m = 200/16 = 12.5$. However, given the piston seals friction on the inside of ЦНД and ЦВД, the multiplier coefficient is 20. In this case, nominal pressure РЖНД in the pump outlet can create pressure РЖВД more than 200 МПа. You can ensure the horizontal and vertical placement of the pressure chamber. Parameter of liquid food, which is has to be measured is the temperature distribution over the sample volume. Sketch of thermocouples block (temperature sensor unit) is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Sketch of thermocouples block

The study used a copper-constantan thermocouple. In three horizontal planes (pl. 1, 2 and 3) there are seven cylindrical thermopairs (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7). In the measurements block thermocouple with the sample (Обр) is isolated from the process fluid pressure by insulation (ИМ). Arrangement of the sample and the thermocouple unit in a high-pressure transducers and ultrasonic unit is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Arrangement of the sample and the thermocouple unit in a pressure vessel

The temperatures of the sample with labels of location of thermocouples are recorded in real time. Documentation of data carried out graphically and as a text file that is automatically created by the management of the experimental research. The desired temperature of the sample is created, maintained and controlled automatically. At a given temperature, fluid pressure in the chamber is automatically generated with a hydraulic pump multiplier.

Control pressure value of the working fluid due as shown by the pressure sensor. A block dia-

gram of the control interface system is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. A block diagram of the installation control interface

So, from the above, we can draw the following conclusions: the authors conducted a literature search to ascertain the state of the problem of food production in the combined processes, processing of raw materials and food products, based methodologies of hardware-experimental studies on the use of combined technologies in food industry, developed design diagram of the experimental setup for studies of the combined action of high pressure, temperature and ultrasound on food raw materials and products, revealed the appointment of separate modules and developed a system with automated control of the research process. Direction of future research is to create the appropriate research equipment, the development of automatic process control experimental trials in the use of high pressure and ultrasound for the treatment of food products and raw materials, research, distribution of temperature in different points of the food sample.

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THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL FACTORS ON REDUCING PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS IN SUNFLOWER SEED KERNELS

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Abstract: *The study revealed to a technological factors which are responding to reduced phenolic compounds and Chlorogenic acid, in whole-grain or broken sunflower seeds during its hydrothermal treatment. It is important to point out that, the sensory analysis of organoleptic properties was obtained in the hydrothermal treated samples.*

Keywords: *sunflower seed kernels, phenolic compounds, Chlorogenic acid, hydrothermal processing, organoleptic properties*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the production of food and semi finished products from Sour milk cheese are increasing. In accordance with the current global financial crisis on the dairy industry in Ukraine, and deficit of raw materials, particularly Sour milk cheese [1, 2], of course, changes in dietary consumption pattern in Ukrainian and essential nutrients deficiency [3, 4] updated searching alternative sources of raw materials and diversification by finding and developing new products, one with higher quality, new features, and higher value in use In all to create successful new products [1].

The special role, plans for new products of the plant as row that contain the essential nutrients in their bodies, as oilseeds [5]. Compares oilseeds, Sunflower seeds are important source of the functional components (protein and oil) and rich chemical composition, particularly confectionery sunflower varieties, is the basic form in Ukraine and traditionally are used both whole and in the powdered form in many food technologies [6]. Market analysis of culinary products based on Sour milk cheese showed that sunflower seed no use in it at all. The major problem is the lack of scientific basis.

The product of the invention is an improved a type of disperse systems, emulsion (hereinafter – the emulsion) based on the sunflower seed kernels [7] with the low-fat Sour milk cheese, create semi-product of cheese composition [8], which will be used in the cooking products with the possibility of further inclusion the required prescription ingredients (flour, sugar, egg, vegetable fillers, flavoring agents, etc.).

It should be noted that one of the major problems that limit the use of the sunflower seed kernels in the products based on Sour milk cheese, is the presence of phenolic compounds (70% of the total content of phenolic compounds is Chlorogenic acid) [9-10]. Under heat treatment, phenolic compounds has led to decrease biological value of the proteins and browning [9-10].

This problem is one the most specific object of the scientific research [10, 11]. It should be emphasized that, one of the important tasks of a new culinary products based on Sore milk cheese involving sunflower seed kernels is to provide high organoleptic characteristics, such as bright color. In order to this problem, remove or substantial reduce the phenolic compounds in the sunflower seed kernels is too nessasery.

Famous research, [10] ensure that phenolic compounds due to small size of their molecules, are soluble in acidic solution of Capillary-Porous Structures in backing fabric sunflower seed kernels, give them possibility passing through the semipermeable cell membrane in difference with protein and oil molecules in aqueous acid solution. In accordance with the present knowledge, hydrothermal processing sunflower seed kernels reduce content of the phenolic compounds. This large molecules (protein and oil) will not be passed through of the cell membranes and remain in the cells.

As we know, among the organic acids, Citric acid which is the prevalence and accessibility in cooking products, As the known requirements for solvents [12] the use of an aqueous solution of citric acid should be preferred: this solution is characterized phenolic compounds, specially acid

chlorogenic, and in difference with the basic nutrients – protein (globular fractions in protein complex) and lipids.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

The objectives of this experiment are:

- determining the influence of technological factors on the reduction of phenolic compounds in the sunflower seed kernels during its hydrothermal treatment;
- the sensory analysis of organoleptic properties in the hydrothermal treatment sunflower seed kernels;
- scientific substantiation of hydrothermal processing on sunflower seed kernels.

The experimental conditions

In the preferred embodiment of the present invention, the seed coat of seed kernels are removed. In view of the known factors that affect the extraction process [12], was selected the dispersion prepared – whole or broken sunflower seed kernels particle size in the range $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$, $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$, and $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$ m, which were obtained by fractionation of seed kernels after removing the seed coat.

Hydrothermal treatment of fractional seed kernels performed by steeping it in a solution of citric acid at pH $4,0 \pm 0,1$ at 20 ± 2 , 40 ± 2 , 60 ± 2 , 80 ± 2 °C. Based on famous scientific observations [13] in order to remove phenolic compounds, rational ratio solid: extractant should be as (1 : 10-15). In view of this, hydromodel of hydrothermal treatment (ratio sunflower seed kernels : acid solvent) in the first stage of

research selected 1 : 10 with an opportunity to further refine.

Should note that, to determine total amount of phenolic compounds with chlorogenic acid, used colorimetric method with Folin-Denis reagent. [14] Chopped seed kernel samples are weighed $(8-10) \times 10^{-3}$ kg, an accuracy of 1×10^{-5} kg, filled with 96% alcohol. Designate its final concentration 80% vol., boiled on a water bath under reflux for 10×60 s, cooled and closed stopper. After that, obtained alcohol extract was poured and samples triturated, by repeated washing with an aqueous solution of 80 % ethyl alcohol, on a Buchner funnel and filtered.

Focus on the completeness of the extraction phenolic compounds, checked by reaction with a solution of 15 % NaOH, should notice that when heating the solution, it should not turn yellow. In order to accurately determine the concentration of phenolic compounds in the working solutions should be in the range of 0,01 to 0,15 mg/cm³, while the concentration of ethanol is 50 % vol. In the case where the content phenolic compounds in solution was above the specified, it was separated to several times. To 1 cm³ ready extract was added 0,3 cm³ reagent Folin-Denis, mixed well, exactly after 20 s, added 5 cm³, 20 % Na₂CO₃ and after 30 s with the optical density was measured at a wavelength 725-730 nm photocolimeters in a 5×10^{-3} m cuvette.

The control was water with the addition of all specified reagents. Simultaneously determine the moisture contents in the samples seed kernels. To calculate the amount of phenolic compounds was found from calibration curve for chlorogenic acid.

Determine the total number of phenolic compounds with chlorogenic acid in terms of the dry matter content shown in the formula:

$$x = \frac{a \times V \times p \times 100 \times 100}{h \times (100 - W)},$$

Where x – the total amount of phenolic compounds in terms of the dry matter, mg/100 g of dry matter;

a – the content of chlorogenic acid, derived from a calibration graph mg/cm³;

V – Volume of alcoholic extract, cm³;

p – The dilution;

h – Mass of sample, g;

W – Moisture of the sample %

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In terms of the reported mechanism, release phenolic compounds by hydrothermal treatment

from the seed kernel tissues is similarly complex mass transfer, involving dialysis, dilution and diffusion. Generally, based on the laws of mass transfer [12], Influence of factors on this process described. According to the theory of mass transfer, the diffusion of phenolic compounds is accelerated with increasing temperature, dispersion seed kernel particles, difference in concentrations between the particles of plant tissue and extragent and decreasing the viscosity of the extragent and size of the molecules that extracted. At the beginning stage of the extraction process, acidic solution of the extragent penetrating into plant tissues sunflower seed kernels.

At first on the macro, micro-cracks, and then on intercellular pores, extragent reaches the cells and diffuses through the cell walls. During the penetration of the extragent into the cell, its contents begin hydrate and dissolve into solution.

Due to difference concentration dissolved substances in and out the cell, begins the dialysis – transfer low molecular weight compounds in the other direction through the cell wall, First in the extragent, which is located in the intercellular pores, and then in extragent, which fills the micro-and macro-cracks and, in the end, the extragent that removes the particles of plant tissue sunflower seed kernels. Thus the speed of

penetration solvent and solute is usually much higher than internal diffusion.

Figure 1 shows that decrease the residual content of phenolic compounds occurs with increasing extraction temperature and reducing the particle size of sunflower seed kernels. As seen at $60 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ and $80 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ remove of phenolic compounds is intensively than at $20 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ and $40 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$.

Obviously, due to the integrity of the cell structure and a complication the diffusion process, the longest extraction of phenolic compounds is from whole sunflower seed kernels. Comparison of efficiency in removing phenol compounds was estimated by organoleptic characteristics hydrothermal sunflower seed kernels. As a result, various freed from phenolic compounds, acquired different color, taste and smell.

It should be mentioned that the formation of organoleptic characteristics, affected by the temperature, duration of the hydrothermal treatment and the particle size of sunflower seed kernels. To determine the reasonable range of these parameters was performed organoleptic evaluation of the milled samples after the hydrothermal treatment. Sensory analysis techniques have developed by using a well-defined 5-point scale (Table 1

Table 1 – Sensory evaluation on a 5-point scale for the sample of sunflower seed kernels after hydrothermal treatment

Quality indicators	Weight-coefficients	Quality level				
		5	4	3	2	1
Color (at a residual content of phenolic compounds,%)	0,6	White with slight light gray tint (less than 1,0)	Light gray (1,0 to 1,3)	gray (1,3 to 1,7)	Taupe (1,7 to 2,2)	Clearly pronounced dark gray (more than 2,2)
Taste	0,3	Impersonal, pure flavors no sunflower oil	Impersonal with a slight flavor and sunflower oil	No strong taste of sunflower with a taste of oil	Taste of sunflower with signs of damage	Clearly pronounced taste of sunflower and a significant flavor of oil with signs of spoilage
Odor	0,1	Impersonal, odorless oil and sunflower	Impersonal, with a slight smell of oil and sunflower	No distinct smell of sunflower and oil	Taste of sunflower with little taste of oil with signs spoilage	Explicitly smell of sunflower and oil with signs of spoilage

Following the results, establishing a connection between residual content of phenolic compounds, color hydrothermally treated sunflower seed kernels and scoping. So, when the

content of phenolic compounds is less than 1,0 % after hydrothermal treatment samples were characterized in white with light gray tint, when the content of phenolic compounds in the range

of 1,0-1,3 % – light gray, with 1,3-1,7 % – gray, with 1,7-2,2 % – dark gray, and when the content of these compounds more than 2,2 % of the samples had dark gray. In view of these data was established reasonable selectivity to phenolic compounds (Fig. 1, D), which allows to achievement crushed fractionated sunflower seed kernels and defines the duration and temperature of the process. View to the scale based sensory evaluation considering the weight coefficients of

the samples (Table 1), conduct different sensory evaluation tests on the samples of sunflower seed kernels during hydrothermal treatment. In the course of this study, have found that the color and the taste, based the forming of organoleptic properties sunflower seed kernels samples. Data in table 2 shows the technological modes of hydrothermal treatment, in which the samples have highest scored.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the residual content phenolic compounds (W, %) in sunflower seed kernels with different size, $\times 10^{-3}$ m: 1 – (1-2), 2 – (2-3), 3 – (3-4), 4 – whole, temperatures, °C: a – 80 ± 2 , b – 60 ± 2 , c – 40 ± 2 , d – 20 ± 2 and sensory evaluation of organoleptic characteristics of the samples, respectively – 1a, 2a, 3a, 4a. I – reasonable range of phenolic compounds.

Table 2 – Study organoleptic properties of sunflower seed kernels during hydrothermal treatment

Temperature hydrothermal treatment of, °C	Scoping organoleptic properties (b) and duration of hydrothermal treatment of (τ) $\times 60$ s with particle sizes of sunflower seed kernels (d), $\times 10^{-3}$ m							
	d (1-2)		d (2-3)		d (3-4)		d (whole)	
	b	τ	b	τ	b	τ	b	τ
80 ± 2	4,15	$20,0 \pm 0,5$	4,02	$45,0 \pm 1,0$	4,00	$60,0 \pm 1,5$	3,23	240 ± 5
60 ± 2	4,95	$40,0 \pm 1,0$	4,97	$75,0 \pm 1,5$	4,97	$120,0 \pm 2,0$	3,51	240 ± 5
40 ± 2	2,86	240 ± 5	2,84	360 ± 5	2,81	480 ± 10	2,09	480 ± 10
20 ± 2	2,64	180 ± 3	2,65	480 ± 10	1,99	720 ± 12	1,94	960 ± 15

It must be emphasized that the scoring curves were extreme at 60 ± 2 °C and 80 ± 2 °C (Fig. 1, a, b – curves 1a-4a) and 40 ± 2 °C (Fig. 1, c – curves 3a, 4a), due to the deterioration of taste and smell under hydrothermal treatment above the specified duration (Table 2). For the samples of sunflower seed kernels, hydrothermally treated are at 20 ± 2 °C and 40 ± 2 °C (Fig. 1, c – curves 1a, 2a, d – curves 1a-4a), scoping reached a maximum at the maximum duration of the hydrothermal treatment. The results showed (Fig. 1, b) reasonably achieving range of phenolic compounds is possible at temperatures of 60 ± 2 °C

and 80 ± 2 °C. In this case, highest numerical score (4,00-4,97) during hydrothermal treatment of the samples occur at the particle size (1-2), (2-3) and (3-4) $\times 10^{-3}$ m (Table 2). It should be noted that the hydrothermal treatment at a temperature 80 ± 2 °C and the specified duration (Table 2) gave the samples of sunflower seed kernels specific taste and smell with the signs of rancid butter, which is obviously due to the hydrolytic oxidative rancidity of the fats [15]. Hydrothermally treated of sunflower seed kernels at 60 ± 2 °C were characterized by white color light gray shade with an impersonal taste and smell without taste and smell of rancid butter

Fig. 2. Dynamics of residual phenolic compounds in fractionated crushed sunflower kernel with particles, $\times 10^{-3}$ m: a – (1-2), b – (2-3), c – (3-4) after hydrothermal treatment at hydromodel: 1 – 1 : 5, 2 – 1 : 10, 3 – 1 : 15, 4 – 1 : 20 at 60 ± 2 °C. I – reasonable range of phenolic compounds

The residual amount of phenolic compounds in them was 33-36 % of the total content that means 0,99-0,92 % of dry matter of sunflower seed kernels. It is interesting to point out that, the hydrothermal treatment with extreme temperature and duration (Fig. 1, a – curve 1) 78,2 % of phenolic compounds can remove up. The finding data of the current study are consistent with the literature [10], approximately 21 % of these compounds are associated with a protein complex in sunflower seed kernels, so they can't be fully separated with acid extraction.

In the next stage of the research, was studied effect of hydraulic module of the hydrothermal treatment on residual content of phenolic compounds in sunflower seed kernels with specific range of the temperature and particle size. For this purpose was determined the residual content of phenolic compounds in the crushed sunflower seed kernels with particle size $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$ m, $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$ m, $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$ m at a temperature of $60 \pm 2^\circ$ C and hydraulic module 1 : 5, 1 : 10, 1 : 15 and 1 : 20.

According to the data, (Fig. 2) there is a general tendency to increase the intensity of removal phenolic compounds and the reduction of their content with increasing hydraulic module. The obtained results suggest that the hydrothermal treatment with hydraulic module 1 : 5 (Fig. 2, 1, 2, 3, curve 1) does not allow achieve a certain reasonable range of phenolic compounds (Fig. 1, 2, I – the rational limits for phenolic compounds), which, according to previous studies should not be higher than 1,0 % (Table 1). The residual content of phenolic compounds in the samples with particle sizes $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$ m, $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$ m and $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$ m, with hydraulic module, are respectively 1,11-1,12, 1,25-1,28 and 1,43-1,45 %.

Hydrothermal treatment with hydraulic module from 1 : 10 and above offers the possibility of obtaining hydrothermally treated sunflower seed kernels with a 1,0 % residual content of phenolic compounds In this case, with increasing hydraulic module ratio 1 : 10, 1 : 15,

1 : 20, time to reach a reasonable range of phenolic compounds decreases: for the samples with the particle size $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$ m respectively (40 ± 1) , (34 ± 1) , $(30 \pm 1) \times 60$ s, with a particle size $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$ m – $(75,0 \pm 1,5)$, (65 ± 1) and $(60 \pm 1) \times 60$ s, and with a particle size $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$ m – (100 ± 2) , (90 ± 1) and $(85 \pm 1) \times 60$ s. Analyzing data show that increasing the ratio of hydraulic module 1 : 10, 1,5 and 2 times (hydromodel 1 : 15 and 1 : 20) a time for limit phenolic compounds is reduced slightly: 1,18 and 1,50 times for samples with particle sizes $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$ m, 1,15 and 1,25 times for the samples with particle sizes $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$ m, 1,11 and 1,18 times for samples with particle sizes $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$ m.

CONCLUSIONS

Summarize the results of research, can be stated on the hydrothermal treatment of crushed sunflower seed kernels with particle size $(1-2) \times 10^{-3}$, $(2-3) \times 10^{-3}$ and $(3-4) \times 10^{-3}$ m at a temperature of $60 \pm 2^\circ$ C and duration no more than $(40 \pm 1) \times 60$ s, $(75,0 \pm 1,5) \times 60$ s and $(100 \pm 2) \times 60$ s. Thus, in our opinion from rational use of water resources point of view, hydrothermal treatment adjustable with hydromodel at 1 : 10. Specified process allows to get sunflower seed kernels with low phenolic compounds, high organoleptic characteristics and a light color, which satisfies each of the requirements for emulsion and in composition, curds.

In such a way, following the development of science-based emulsion technology on the basis of sunflower seed kernels with reduction phenolic compounds will provide new opportunities for using plant material in the culinary products based on the compositional curd products using the developed emulsions creating a new class of food products with regulate nutritional value, amino acid and fatty acid composition.

[http://ipdo.kiev.ua/index.php?](http://ipdo.kiev.ua/index.php?option=comcontent&view=article&id=259)

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THERMODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF HEAT EXCHANGING APPLIANCES

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Abstract: *The article examines the methodology of thermodynamic analysis and the optimization of heaters and heat exchangers of heat engineering complex of saccharine industry. The authors suggest noncyclic approach to the analysis of efficiency of heat exchanging apparatus, the basis of which is irrefutable fact that irreversibility as physical reason of inefficiency of technical heat engineering systems really exists. Thermodynamic analysis, which was mentioned in the article, assumes determination of measure of irreversibility of processes in the apparatus and energetic efficiency of apparatus in the whole with the help of exceptionally entropy. The measures taken to improve energetic efficiency of apparatus of saccharine factory on the example of the first group of juice heating in front of evaporator system using the given methodology, were fully analyzed.*

Key words: *thermodynamics, heat exchange, process, entropy, exergy of warmth.*

1. Introduction

Heat exchanging apparatus of heat engineering system of saccharine industry are a part of general energy supply allocation of an enterprise as the major secondary heat and electrical energy user, which makes it difficult to analyze and optimize these apparatus. That consequently requires systematic approach with the usage of applicable methods.

It is obvious that nowadays such major characteristics as “area of thermoexchange surface” and “coefficient of efficiency” are traditionally used in saccharine industry. That is not enough, as while comparing constructionally different HEAs it makes no sense to compare relation between area of thermoexchanging surface and its characteristics. The usage of exergy method of thermodynamic analysis [3] (which is widely used while analyzing technical systems – work generators) contradicts the fundamental principles of methodology of

optimization of thermoexchanging processes and systems.

The issue of choice of analysis of effectiveness of HEA was reviewed by the authors in [1,2], where the expediency of usage of non-cyclic entropy method for thermodynamical analysis and HEA optimization, as well as energetic balance method for composing energy model of HEA performance is substantiated.

Adhering to producers’ terminology, HEA of “condensate-juice” type is called as “heat exchangers”, and HEA of “steam-liquid” type – as “heaters”.

According to non-cycle entropy method technique [1, 2], integrated thermodynamic analysis assumes the determination of measure of irreversibility of processes, that occurs in HEA, the sources of which are heat exchanging at the finite variance of temperatures, the dissipation of mechanic energy of heat transfer medium currents and heat exchanging with the environment.

Fig. 1. Before the folding of entropy balance of HEA

The quantitative characteristics of irreversibility is increasing of entropy of isolated system, which determines from the entropy balance of ABC system (Fig. 1), which consists of 3 subsystems: A, B, and C (A is heating heat transfer medium subsystem, B - heat transfer medium subsystem, C – environment subsystem).

In general, entropy balance of HEA is agglomerated with the help of following simplifications:

– change of kinetic and potential energy is neglected;

– for heat transfer mediums, in which transition between preset thermodynamic states is followed by temperature changes (Fig. 2 a, 2 b), change of thermal qualities is not considerable, which allows to introduce medium thermodynamic temperature:

$$T_m = \frac{T^{in} - T^{out}}{\ln \frac{T^{in}}{T^{out}}} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Change of thermodynamical states of hot and cold heat transfer media: a – in heat transfer medium, b – in heater

Written form of entropy is grounded on its qualities and assumes that all its parts are absolute values; entropy can be either brought in or taken out together with the streams of substance and heat, and increase because of the irreversibility of the processes.

Entropy balance of every subsystem (Fig. 1) looks like this:

Entropy balance of subsystem A:

$$m_1 s_1^{in} + \frac{E_1^d}{T_{m_1}} = m_1 s_1^{out} + \frac{Q}{T_{m_1}} + \frac{Q_0}{T_{m_1}} ; \quad (2)$$

Entropy balance of subsystem B:

$$m_2 s_2^{in} + \frac{Q}{T_{m_2}} + \frac{E_2^d}{T_{m_2}} = m_2 s_2^{out} ; \quad (3)$$

Entropy balance of subsystem C:

$$\Delta S_C = \frac{Q_0}{T_0} . \quad (4)$$

Estimating entropy additivity, in another words, $DS_{ABC} = DS_A + DS_B + DS_C$, and the fact that AB subsystem together with C subsystem create generally isolated adiabatic system ABC (concluded from the boundary line quantities of the system), for

which entropy change equals general entropy increase fom irreversibility of the processes: $\Delta S_{ABC} = \Delta S_{irrev}^{tot}$. It can be written in the following way:

$$\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot} = m_1 s_1^{out} + m_2 s_2^{out} - (m_1 s_1^{in} + m_2 s_2^{in}) + \frac{Q_0}{T_0}, \quad (5)$$

or

$$\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot} = \left(\frac{Q}{T_{m_2}} - \frac{Q}{T_{m_1}} \right) + \left(\frac{Q_0}{T_0} - \frac{Q_0}{T_{m_1}} \right) + \frac{E_1^d}{T_{m_1}} + \frac{E_2^d}{T_{m_2}}. \quad (6)$$

We rewrite the equation (6) in general view:

$$\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot} = \Delta S_{irrev}^T + \Delta S_{irrev}^0 + \sum \Delta S_{irrev}^p, \quad (7)$$

In which $\Delta S_{irrev}^T = \frac{Q}{T_{m_2}} - \frac{Q}{T_{m_1}}$ - is increasing of system

entropy, conditioned by irreverence of heat exchange between subsystems A and B; W/K;

$\Delta S_{irrev}^0 = \frac{Q_0}{T_0} - \frac{Q_0}{T_{m_1}}$ - increasing of entropy at

dissipation of mechanical energy of streams of heat

transfer medium (in case of the heaters $E_1^d / T_{m_1} = 0$) W/K.

Thermodynamical efficiency of HEA, considering the irreverence of the processes, is defined by non-dimensional coefficients: entropy coefficient of thermodynamical efficiency:

$$\eta_s^p = 1 - \frac{\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot}}{\Delta S_{irrev}^{max}}; \quad (8)$$

Or entropy coefficient of thermodynamical non-efficiency:

$$\eta_s^{imp} = \frac{\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot}}{\Delta S_{irrev}^{max}}, \quad (9)$$

While

$$\eta_s^{imp} + \eta_s^p = 1. \quad (10)$$

In which ΔS_{irrev}^{tot} - is increasing of entropy of isolated system, that goes across to two given states, W/K; ΔS_{irrev}^{max} - maximal possible increasing of entropy of adiabatic system - system passes from given state to the state of thermodynamic balance with the environment, W/K.

Coefficients (8) and (9) do not have known (discovered) drawbacks of performance factor (energetic, exergy), as they characterize the degree of diversion of real system from reverent in structure borders of the second thermodynamic law. Let us explain this.

Including the fact that the state of balance of isolated system is defined by the maximum of its

entropy (consequence of the second thermodynamic law) and restrictions, imposed by the nature on the operation of technical systems (energy has technical meaning till it has the potential different from the one of the environment), denominator of equations 8 and 9 is used as the standard of comparison.

It means that ΔS_{irrev}^{max} , being the result of heat exchanging of hypothetical TS (system A) with the environment (system C) (pic. 3), which quantitatively characterizes maximal irreversibility at given characteristics of environment and is calculated with the help of the following equation (Fig. 3):

$$\Delta S_{irrev}^{max} = m_1(s_0 - s_1) + \frac{Q_0}{T_0} + \frac{E_1^d}{T_0} + \frac{E_2^d}{T_0}, \tag{11}$$

In which s_0 - is specific entropy of heating heat transfer medium at the temperature of environment, J/(kg/K).

Fig. 3. Hypothetic TS

While analyzing the heaters in equation (6) $T_{m1} = T_{1s}$ - the temperature of saturation of dry saturated steam, and $E_1^d / T_0 = 0$.

The efficiency of functioning of HEA – local effectiveness of potential usage of heat transfer medium (temperature), including dissipation

$$\eta_s = \frac{\Delta S_{irrev}^{min}}{\Delta S_{irrev}^{tot}}, \tag{12}$$

In which ΔS_{irrev}^{min} - is a minimal entropy increasing because of heat exchanging irreverence in HEA, $\Delta S_{irrev}^{min} = Q(T_{m1}^{min} - T_{m2}) / (T_{m1}^{min} T_{m2})$, W/K, Q – true heat effectiveness of HEA, W; T_{m2} - medium thermodynamic temperature of the heating up heat transfer medium, K; T_{m1}^{min} - minimal possible medium thermodynamic temperature of heating heat transfer medium, K. For heaters $T_{m1}^{min} = T_{1s}^{min}$ (Fig. 4 a); for heat transfer media with large mass account thermal

processes in given temperature interval – defined entropy coefficient of HEA effectiveness:

capacity of heating heat transfer medium according to equation 6 and pic. 4 b $T_{m1}^{min} = (T_{1min}^{in} - T_{1min}^{out}) / (\ln T_{1min}^{in} / T_{1min}^{out})$, thus $T_{1min}^{in} = T_2^{out}$; for heat exchangers with larger mass account thermal capacity of heating up heat transfer medium T_{m1}^{min} is calculated analogically, including $T_{1min}^{out} = T_2^{in}$ (Fig. 4 c).

Fig. 4. Before defining ΔS_{irrev}^{min} : a- in the heater; b – in the heater with bigger mass consumptive thermal capacity of heat transfer medium; c – in heater with bigger mass consumptive thermal capacity of heating heat transfer medium

2. Analysis of groups of heaters based on developed coefficients η_{sp} and η_s

Let us consider detailed features of usage of suggested coefficients with an example of heaters' analysis of the first group of the juice heaters in front of evaporator system for saccharine factory with

efficiency of 6000 tons of beet processing per day with heading the standards for increasing their efficiency.

Parameters of job of heating group: juice expense – 118 % up to beetroot mass; juice temperature in front of the heater – 87 °C; temperature of saturation of the heating steam – 107 °C.

Fig.5. Relation between entropy coefficient of thermodynamic efficiency of group of heating of the heaters and area of heat exchanging surface

Fig .6. Relation between entropy coefficient of efficiency of heating group of the heaters and area of the heat exchanging surface

3. Increasing of the area of heat exchange F with the value of K.

By calculation and analysis of effectiveness of heating groups, that consist of one, two, three sequentially by juice linked ten-course heaters with $F = 300 \text{ m}^2$ of every single one (PDS-10-300), the velocity of juice motion in pipes equals $\omega = 1,38 \text{ m/s}$ (the scum formation is not included). On picture 5 and 6 dynamics of coefficient variation with F increasing at constant k is mentioned. As it was expected, with increasing of F both the coefficients increase to some maximum value, which is caused by the defining influence on general irreverence of reduction of irreverence of heat exchange. In addition, although the range in coefficients' change is different, maximum of the curve of each of them corresponds equal area of heat exchange.

4. Increasing of coefficient of heat transfer K

4.1. In heaters with hydraulically smooth pipes (ducts) – increasing of liquid motion velocity.

4.1.1 The effectiveness of heating groups, that consist of one, two, three sequentially switched on juice ten-coursed heaters with $F = 200 \text{ m}^2$ for each (PDS-10-200), was calculated and analyzed. The juice velocity in pipes equals $\omega = 2,08 \text{ m/s}$. The results, given on picture 5 and 6, show that the value of coefficients are less than those received in previous case for all the range variation of F, but the dynamics of their change is bigger (depends from the velocity), it is vividly demonstrated by η_s (Fig. 6).

At the same time, extremum is expressed more accurately and it is biased left.

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4.1.2. The similar result is received for sectional heaters with sequentially switched sections, with 42 tubes 30/33 mm in diameter each and 5,2 m long, velocity of juice in which makes $\omega = 2,86 \text{ m/s}$. It can be seen from the pictures, that the increase of velocity of motion of heat-carrier, despite the intensification of heat exchange, causes decrease both thermodynamical efficiency and its complex energetic efficiency.

4.2. Usage of heaters with heat exchange intensification. Heating groups were calculated and analyzed. They consist of platelet heater, juice motion velocity in pipes of which equals $\omega = 0,3 \text{ m/s}$. on pic. 5 can be seen the dynamics of change of entropy coefficient of thermodynamic efficiency of heating group, and on pic. 6 – dynamics of change of entropy coefficient of efficiency of heating group with increasing of F at constant k. In both cases platelet heater provides better efficiency with less area of heat exchange.

Conclusions

Suggested technique of thermodynamic analysis assumes scientifically proved systematic approach to comparative analysis and different construction, that, obviously, is suitable to do with the help of entropy coefficient of efficiency, as well as for defining their thermodynamic efficiency in margins of sugar plant. The last can be achieved with the help of using entropy coefficient of thermodynamic efficiency and allows to analyze different heat exchanging systems for defining the level of their influence on general energetic efficiency of sugar plant.

BIOTECHNOLOGY IN THE MEAT INDUSTRY

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Abstract. The paper presents experimental studies on an integrated approach to providing high quality and biological safety of meat products using biotechnology techniques.

Key words: quality, biotechnology, innovation, ecology, bio safety.

Introduction

Meat products are related to the list of strategically important as providing a full human diet of albuminous component. Therefore a guarantee of quality and safety is one of the priority tasks of the modern food industry. Considering economic, environmental and social situation of the state, the problem of quality and food safety should be seen and connect to the issue of preserving the gene pool of the nation, so the development of national biotechnology the production of quality and safe meat products is extremely important.

According to current requirements of quality and safety of meat products collective of authors developed a complex approach to solution this issue. The essence of the a comprehensive approach is the simultaneous use:

- antimicrobial preparations based on the of the catholyte pH = 11-12, ORP = -600 ± 50 mV;
- bacterial preparation "Aromalakt", which consists of starter cultures (*Lactobacillus plantarum* 21, *Pediococcus acidilactici* 55, *Staphylococcus xylosus* 45, *Debaryomyces hansenii* Dhi);

- preparation for the surface treatment developed by on the basis of the anolyte pH = 3-3,4, ORP = +1000 ± 50 mV.

The main technological task of the developed a comprehensive approach was prolonging the shelf life of boiled sausages to 10 days with a stable high level of quality and biological safety, while reducing residual content of sodium nitrite in the finished product.

The advanced technology is implemented by: adding to meat system bacterial drug "Aromalakt" after grinding raw materials, in an amount 100g/100 kg, making the stage of cutting antimicrobial preparations instead of the water component of recipe, the surface treatment cooked sausage bactericidal agent on the basis anolyte for 15 minutes instead of the usual water at the stage cooling.

To determine the lowest possible introduction of sodium nitrite in meat products and evaluation was prepared four samples: 1st - control, 2 nd, 3 rd and 4 th - with the addition of sodium nitrite in amounts of 3, 5 and 7.5 mg per 100 g of raw material, respectively. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The results of research of using "Aromalakt"

Indicator	Samples of cooked sausages			
	1 – Control 0,0075% NaNO ₂	2 – Research «Aromalakt»+ 0,0075% NaNO ₂	3 – Research «Aromalakt» + 0,005% NaNO ₂	4 – Research «Aromalakt» + 0,003% NaNO ₂
Mass portion of sodium nitrite, %	0,0047±0,00002	revealed traces	revealed traces	revealed traces
Number of nitrozopihments, %	68,15±0,56	78,93±0,45	77,48±0,59	70,11±0,44

Determination of residual sodium nitrite the experimental samples (№ 2, 3, 4) compared showed no nitrite ions (accuracy ± 0,00002%) in with control (№ 1). Samples with different residual

nitrite content compared with the control, confirming the pronounced nitrytreduktiv activity of "Aromalakt." These data suggest the possibility of reducing the introduction of sodium nitrite in cooked sausages from 0.0075% to 0.003%, while the introduction of bacterial formulation "Aromalakt."

The further researches were carried out on the basis of the results of the previous two samples of

cooked sausage - control produced by the standard technique of introducing sodium nitrite is 7.5 mg per 100 g of raw research - produced by advanced biotechnology, introduction of sodium nitrite is 3 mg per 100 g.

Results of the study of the chemical composition of control and experimental samples of cooked sausages are presented in Figure 2.

Fig 1. Chemical composition of cooked sausages

Data analysis in Figure 1 indicate that the control and experimental samples of cooked sausages meet the requirements regarding quality. Making of prototypes sausages antimicrobial agents and bacterial drug has a positive impact on the overall distribution of the components, which is an advantage compared to controls. Reducing the fat content and increase protein content reduces the total calorie product that meets current trends in

healthy eating. It should also be noted increase in the moisture content of the sample, indicating that the improved distribution and binding moisture in the product.

Degustation committee noted that the organoleptic quality prototypes cooked sausage in dynamic storage significantly superior to control, and have been stable high quality for 10 days.

Fig. 2. Change the water activity a_w during storage of samples cooked sausages

Analysis of the data Figure 2 shows that in the experimental samples water activity is less than in the control and in dynamic storage does not exceed the value of 0.9668, which is valid and indicates

the level of resistance to the meat of activity microflora.

The next stage of the research was to study the dynamics of changes in the lipid fraction of boiled

sausages for a guaranteed shelf and two reserve days. Assessment of sustainability conducted on the characteristics of acid, peroxide and tiobarbitur numbers. The results indicate that, at 10 days of storage peroxide, acid and tiobarbitur number of experimental sausages began to within acceptable standards regulations.

Improved resilience to lipid fraction oxidative processes due to antioxidant action of antimicrobial agents, as well as the pattern appears in the process damage the surface treatment bactericidal agent.

The main criterion for for a positive Hygienic Assessment of shelf life of products is the absence negative dynamics of the whole complex of the studied parameters.

During the study, microbiological samples during storage of cooked sausages found in control samples for 5 days develop yeast. Sanitation indicators prototypes cooked sausages meet all safety requirements for the guaranteed shelf and two reserve days. This trend is explained by the complex action of bacterial drug "Aromalakt" antimicrobial agents and bactericidal drug for the surface treatment of cooked sausage.

Conclusions

As a result of comprehensive research hypothesis regarding the use of biotechnological techniques, such as environmentally friendly antimicrobial, bacterial and bacteriostatic drugs to improve comprehensive quality and safety of meat of the product was confirmed experimentally.

These results allow us to recommend an integrated biotechnological approach for prolonging the shelf life of cooked sausage to 10 days with guaranteed high-quality and biological safety and improving environmental hygiene products made by minimizing the level of entry of sodium nitrite to 3 mg per 100 g, which allows you to virtually eliminate its residual content in the product.

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APPLICATIONS IN PRECISION AGRICULTURE OF STABILIZATION SYSTEMS WITH MICRO-SENSORS FOR PHOTO AND VIDEO CAMERAS

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Abstract: *Researches regarding the active cameras stabilization using the micro-sensors signals processing procedure are presented in this paper. The original contribution of the research refers to the necessary steps to develop a system equipped with a micro-controller able to interpret and to process the data provided from a micro-sensorial system and also to transfer the PWM signals to actuators intended to the entire camera system stabilization. The main advantage refers to the costs due to the fact that low cost electronic device could be adapted and programmed to process the signals providing from the sensory system.*

Keywords: *AHRS, micro-sensors, stabilization, agricultural machineries.*

1. Introduction

A higher demand in quality photography and filming is required, especially in precision agriculture applications where environmental parameters, and the capture of various details requests high precision and speed filming that is free of distortions. Distortions elimination takes up a huge task of processing power and so numerous devices are developed in order to soften or eliminate the vibrations of the recording device during the displacement. If improper stabilization device is used during high-speed photographing or filming, the image interpretation could be compromised, which is why stabilization systems are being under pressure to provide better image acquisition during transport.

Actual solutions for cameras stabilization involve: arm stability platforms [1], [2] hand held stabilization systems, arm system stabilization [3], [4]. One solution is the *Steadicam* stabilization system that isolates the movements of the transport device from the camera. *Steadicam* is developed for human operator filming and is made up of a vest, a single or double spring arm and a sled, for mounting of the camera [5], [6].

The paper focuses on an innovative solution to improve the stabilization performances of a filming system by using modified similar *Steadicam* system that contains a 3 direction micro-sensorial platform [5].

The 3-directional micro-sensorial system is the *Attitude Heading Reference System (AHRS)* initially developed for aircrafts. This system is fitted with sensors for each one of the 3 directions of displacement, allowing to obtain and measure the heading (yaw), pitch and roll angles. The electronic block, transmits the position angles values from the sensors to another device (actuator), that will calculate the response value [7]. The rotation around the vertical axis is named the heading angle, the equilibrium (pitch) angle is associated to the angle of attack, the roll angle is the rotation angle around the longitudinal axis with the positive sense to the right. The yaw angle is generated around the vertical axis and the pitch angle is generated around the transversal axis, with positive sense associated to the front part elevation. As a result the micro-sensorial AHRS generates the 3 angles around the X, Y and Z axis (roll, pitch and yaw).

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2. Research methods and materials

In our research, we have used a *AHRS 9 DOF* system, produced by Spark Fun company, with advantages to the costs, dimension and precision. The system has an integrated electronic block, *AHRS 9DOF* micro-sensorial system presented in figure 1, for the acquisition and process of the position data.

The computing and control unit is ensured by the *Atmega162* is a 8-bit microcontroller, with RISC architecture. The microcontroller frequency is 16 MHz, given by the quartz oscillator, placed in the circuit, powered by 2 capacitors with 18 pF.

Fig. 1 *The integrated electronic board used for the data transfer from AHRS 9 DOF system. 1 - ATmega 328 microcontroller; 2 - Serial interface (FTDI compatible); 3 - LPR 530AL, dual axis pitch and roll $\pm 300^\circ/s$ analog gyroscope; 4 - ADXL 345, Digital Accelerometer; 5 - LY530ALH, MEMS motion sensor: high performance $\pm 300^\circ/s$ analog yaw-rate gyroscope; 6 - HMC5843, 3-Axis Digital Compass IC; 7 - SPI interface for ATmega 328 microcontroller programming; 8 - Power ON/OFF Switch; 9 - Reset button.*

The ultra-fast microcontroller cores from the *e-8051* family, became the most popular architecture, produced in different types based on a set of CISC instructions, presenting the following advantages: 8-bit data, 64 kB data bus and address, variants with or without integrated internal and external memory, I/O bidirectional lines without preliminary configuration, RAM memory addressing by bit and byte, at least 16-bit timers, many 1-bit instructions. The main disadvantages identified were the following: slow instruction set, slow data transfer for frequencies higher than 40 MHz, due to the increased number

of clock cycles (4-12), difficult access to the external data (a single address register), faulty compilation in C++ programming.

AVR family are produced by Atmel, are fast, with a single cycle/instruction. The main advantages are: many registers without battery, orthogonal instruction set, 3 registers with address for auto-increasing/decreasing, it can process more than 64 kB of data.

The main advantage of the proposed system refers to the costs due to the fact that low cost electronic device could be adapted and programmed to process the signals providing from the sensory system. The main disadvantages are the following: the instruction set is slowly and redundant.

Due to the analysis to choose the family and the type of the microcontroller, the *8-bit Atmel* range was selected, with RISC architecture and the microcontroller *Atmega 16* with the following characteristics: 28 pin DIP package, 32 kB of program space, 23 I/O channels (6 of them are 10-bit Analog to Digital convertor capable). It runs up to 16MHz with external crystal and it can be programmed in a circuit.

The microcontroller programming was possible using a connector which addresses the data channels MISO, MOSI, SCK and RESET of the ISP (In System Programable) programming interface. This way of programming allows erasing, writing and reading FLASH and EEPROM memories without the microcontroller to be removed from the board.

The board supplying was made through the connector (5) (figure 2) at the voltage of 5V. The led (4) indicates if the board was or not supplied. For the serial communication with the PC, there it was used the serial interface *USART 0* of the microcontroller. The signals providing from the microcontroller were converted into $\pm 12V$ signals using the MAX 232 circuit (7), the converted signals being transferred to the DB9 connector (6). For the communication with AHRS there it was used the *USART 1* interface of the microcontroller. One of the main encountered problems was the voltage difference between the system board (5V) – microcontroller and AHRS sensorial system (3.3 V). For the data transfer, there it was used the TX line (transmission) from the AHRS board to the RX channel of the board containing the microcontroller. The experimental researches proved a good functioning even if was voltage difference between the 2 signals.

Fig. 2. The electronic scheme of the AHRS board with the Atmega microcontroller: 1 – quartz oscillator, 2 – ISP connector, 3 – reset circuit, 4 – supplying state led, 5 – connector for the microcontroller powering, 6 – connector for serial interfacing, 7 – converter circuit for the serial interface, 8 – Atmega 162 microcontroller, 9 – state led to indicate the microcontroller normal functioning, 10 – RX signal for input data to the serial interface

To avoid the 5V voltage signal transfer to the AHRS board we have introduced a rapide diode, BAT85, allowing the unidirectional data transfer from AHRS to the microcontroller.

The microcontroller used 2 signals for the communication with the AHRS board. One signal was linked to the pin 3 of the Atmega 162 microcontroller, named RXD1, signal used for the data receiving to the serial interface USART 0. The data transfer is highlighted by a led that was connected with the signal that came to the pin 39 named PA0.

The voltage regulator circuit for the AHRS board worked through the adjustable resistance and so the output voltage level could be

established. The 9 DOF AHRS board needed a power supply of 3.3 V.

The data transfer improvement. In order to ensure the data transfer and processing for the system ordering, we realized a hardware circuit as shown in figure 3 as block – diagram. It allows ordering the servomotors of the stabilizing system, as actuators, via PC – microcontroller, the later having as input signals the acquired data from the AHRS sensory system. The hardware diagram shows that the mother board incorporates the Atmega 162 microcontroller, which contains 2 serial interfaces, USART 0 and USART 1.

Fig. 3. The hardware diagram for stabilization system ordering

The serial interface USART 0 was bidirectional used for the communication with the PC and the serial interface USART 1 was used for the data receiving from the AHRS system. It was used especially for setting the software program developed by the microcontroller.

The AHRS system is used for reading the position values by the microcontroller and saves it in a temporary buffer pending receipt newline character. After the character receiving the function build phrase was called to separate the string from buffer.

The simplified block (figure 4) – diagram concerning the steps taken for the information acquiring from the AHRS sensorial system is presented below.

The first step represented the sequence to call the subroutine for the character receiving interruption on the USART 1 serial interface. It allowed the data transfer between the AHRS sensorial system and the Atmega 162 microcontroller.

Each subroutine calling was received a character to be temporary save in the RX Buffer.

The second step (figure 5) referred to the calling of the function *Generate Phrase()* to read the buffer content to share the information into several distinct parts, representing words. The function *Generate Phrase()* calling is made after the interrupt service subroutine for character receiving on the serial interface receives the line's end character. The aim is to separate the buffer content into several distinct parts to facilitate the data interpretation providing from the buffer.

Fig. 4. The simplified block-scheme for the data processing.

The buffer content can have the form: *!ANG:-0.27,0.34,-11.39*. The function saves the data into several strings, depending by the separating characters “,” or “:”.

After the function calling, the RXBuffer is passed character by character. The simplified block – diagram presenting the necessary steps to generate and interpret the phrases is presented below.

The block diagram significance is the following:

The block *RXBuffer [LRXBuffer] <> Enter* verifies if the current character represents the end – line character (*LRXBuffer* addresses the character order to be processed).

RXBuffer[LRXBuffer] = ',' or ':' verifies if the current character separates two words. *Word finished New Word* means that if the current character separates 2 words then the string end character is added to the current word end it is proceed to the following word completion.

Add char to current word means that if the current character does not indicates a new line or a separation between 2 distinct words, using “:” or “,” then the current character is added to the current word. *Next char* increments the LRXBuffer variable and to the next cycle the next character from the buffer will be processed. *Exit Generate Phrase* indicates that if the current character is a line – end then the function *Generate Phrase* ends and the *Phrase Interpreting* function will run. After the function *Generate Phrase()* programming sequence we have proceed to the *Phrase Interpreting()* routine programming which role is to call different subroutines depending on the received command. The function has the main role to run different

code sequences depending by the obtained phrase due to the buffer sharing into several sub-strings, named words.

Fig. 5. The block diagram for the Generate Phrase function

Due to the fact that the software application from the board 9DOF AHRS, needed some setting work it was necessary to reprogram the Atmega 328P microcontroller memory. The program that performs mathematical algorithms to determine the 3 angles for roll, pitch and yaw was achieved by the manufacturer using the Arduino software environment.

Fig. 6. The 10-pin to 6-pin conversion board scheme

The programming via USB interface using the Arduino environment was not possible without a compatible boot loader. To address the boot loader compatible with Arduino environment, there it was used the application using a compatible programmer, STK500 and the program AVR Dude. Due to the fact that the board was not equipped with SPI standard 10-pin

connector, addressed by the STK500 compatible programmer, there it was necessary to achieve a 10-pin to 6-pin signal conversion board (figure 6).

3. Results and conclusions

Programming algorithms were successfully applied to stabilize in real time the photo and video cameras during transport. The application used the sensory system to measure in real-time 2 tilting angles of the camera, one defining the rotation around the X axis (roll angle), the other representing the rotation around the Z axis (yaw axis). Based on data interpretation algorithm from Atmega microcontroller it was possible to order 2 actuators so that photo/video cameras keep tilt boundaries in an interval that ensure stability.

The solution provides the following advantages: no human operator present on the stabilizing suspending system and also the efficiency increasing. This was possible due to considerable reduction of camera shake correction necessary time under the influence of disturbing external factors such of wind or balance created by acceleration and deceleration caused by camera movement on suspended cable. Future research will concern the application of the stabilization and processing algorithms and interpretation of data providing from microcontroller to stabilize the photo and video cameras located inside various moving vehicles such as agricultural machineries.

The technology boom of recent years allows us to design new devices using integrated technology. If 15 years ago a computer board of an aircraft was built in mechanic parts, analog electronic representing a considerable volume, the integrated technology today makes possible to reduce the size, weight, response time, costs and accuracy improving. Micro-sensors low price made it possible to use these technologies in the construction of mechanic systems stabilization that equip the cameras used in precision agriculture.

This research described a solution to use these micro-sensors via Atmega microcontrollers for stabilization of cameras that are to be used in applications in precision agriculture.

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NEWS**NEEFOOD 2013**

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